

UNIVERSITY OF MILANO - BICOCCA
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Communication
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Leveraging high-throughput data and unsupervised learning to characterize cancer metabolic heterogeneity

Supervisor: Prof. Dario Pescini

Co-supervisors: Prof.ssa Chiara Damiani, Dott. Bruno Giovanni Galuzzi

Master's degree thesis by:
Luca Milazzo
ID number 856702

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Contents

Abstract	1
Introduction	3
1 Scientific background	7
1.1 Metabolic Networks	7
1.2 Linear programming	9
1.3 Constraint-based modelling	11
1.3.1 FBA	11
1.3.2 pFBA	11
1.3.3 FVA	12
1.3.4 Sensitivity analysis	13
1.4 Flux Sampling	14
1.4.1 Markov Chains	16
1.4.2 Internal Sampling of the Polytope	17
1.4.3 Corner-Based Sampling (CBS)	19
1.4.4 False discoveries and sampling best practises	20
1.4.5 Samples statistics	20
1.5 Omics data integration	23
2 Methods	27
2.1 Cancer Cell Line Encyclopedia	27
2.2 ENGRO 2	30
2.3 Data integration	31
2.3.1 Cell-specific metabolic models	31
2.3.2 scFEA	35
2.4 Preprocessing	41
2.4.1 Transcriptomics denoising: MAGIC	41
2.4.2 Scaling	47
2.4.3 Principal Component Analysis (PCA)	48
2.5 Clustering Analysis	50
2.5.1 Hyperparameters tuning	50
2.5.2 Clusterings comparison	54

2.5.3	Internal Evaluation Metrics	56
2.5.4	External Evaluation Metrics	59
2.5.5	Biomarkers	62
3	Results and discussion	63
3.1	Metabolomics as clustering benchmark	63
3.2	Transcriptomics and metabolomics share similar metabolic phenotypes	66
3.3	INTEGRATE fluxomics does not reflect metabolic profiles . .	68
3.4	MAGIC mitigates RNA-seq noise	71
3.5	MAGIC improves fluxomics prediction	77
3.6	CHRR outperforms CBS in samples clustering	83
3.7	scFEA as promising integration framework	88
4	Conclusions	93
A	Supplementary figures and tables	105
A.1	PCA preprocessing	105
A.2	Metabolomics biomarkers and meta-data	108
A.3	Clustering hyperparameters	112

Abstract

Diseases such as obesity, diabetes and cancer are influenced by various factors, including genetics and environmental conditions. Recent research indicates that metabolic alterations play a significant role in the development and progression of these diseases [1, 2, 3, 4]. However, directly measuring metabolic fluxes remains challenging due to technical and financial constraints. To address this problem, genome-scale metabolic models (GEMs) provide a comprehensive computational framework for predicting reaction fluxes. These models use techniques such as linear programming to numerically simulate metabolism. Consequently, integration methods are employed to incorporate high-throughput omics data within metabolic models to predict fluxomics with higher precision. Unfortunately, their evaluation is limited to just a few fluxes that can be directly measured in the laboratory.

This thesis aims to overcome the limitations of benchmarking integration methods by using intracellular metabolomics as a reference. Two integration methods were applied to 513 different cancer cells from the Cancer Cell Line Encyclopedia (CCLE) [5]: INTEGRATE [6], a constraint-based steady-state method, and scFEA [7], a novel algorithm based on artificial neural networks. Using unsupervised learning techniques, clusters derived from metabolomics, transcriptomics, and fluxomics were compared to evaluate their concordance in recognizing metabolic phenotypes.

A high level of coherence was found between metabolomics and transcriptomics, identifying similar metabolic subpopulations and suggesting the robustness of metabolomics as a benchmark. The results highlighted the necessity, even for bulk samples, of preprocessing the RNA-seq matrix with a denoising algorithm, specifically MAGIC [8]. MAGIC significantly decreased matrix sparsity by revealing lost genetic information and increased the concordance level between metabolomics and inferred INTEGRATE fluxomics. Conversely, scFEA inherently managed to reduce noise and achieved similar performance to the INTEGRATE framework. Overall, neither INTEGRATE nor scFEA drastically outperformed the other in comparing their metabolic clusters with the benchmark. Eventually, clusters identified among metabolomics, transcriptomics and predicted fluxomics can be analyzed by life scientists to extract valuable insights about the biomarkers of the subpopulations.

Introduction

Many physiological and pathological conditions, including cancer, neurodegenerative diseases and aging, exhibit distinct metabolic features. Metabolism is intricately linked to nearly all cellular processes, making it a key indicator of a cell's or organism's physiological state [9]. Genome-scale metabolic models (GEMs), such as Recon [10], encompass all cellular reactions and their connections, allowing for the study of cellular metabolism and physiology.

Although GEMs have provided a solid understanding of the fundamental structure of metabolic pathways, their systemic regulation remains elusive due to technical challenges. Metabolism can be fully characterized by reaction fluxes, which represent the rates at which metabolites are consumed in biochemical reactions. Directly measuring metabolic fluxes using labeled substrates is more complex compared to other omics technologies, such as metabolomics and transcriptomics [11]. This process is expensive, labor-intensive, and difficult to apply at single-cell or spatial resolution. Consequently, metabolic fluxes can currently only be inferred indirectly through experimental techniques and only for a limited set of reactions.

To overcome these limitations, significant efforts have been made to predict metabolic fluxes from high-throughput data, particularly gene expression data from both bulk and single-cell analyses. Transcriptomics technologies, such as RNA-seq [12], measure gene expression at either the single-cell or bulk level and are typically used to predict metabolic fluxes, as gene expression regulates the production of enzymes that catalyze specific cellular reactions. However, cell metabolism is also regulated by intracellular metabolomics, which involves measuring the concentrations of metabolites, the reactants in these reactions, within the cell.

Despite the availability of extensive transcriptomics, proteomics, and metabolomics datasets, a complete understanding of the regulatory mechanisms controlling metabolism requires appropriate integration of these data into predictive models. Constraint-based steady-state models offer a valuable framework for predicting metabolic fluxes using high-throughput omics data [13, 14]. These models are analyzed using the constraint-based modeling (CBM) paradigm, which constructs a mathematical model by constraining network flows through a set of equations. The primary constraint is the steady-state constraint, which assumes that the rates of metabolite consump-

tion and production are balanced. The core equation of these models is $S\vec{v} = \vec{0}$, where S is the stoichiometric matrix of size $m \times r$ (with m metabolites and r reactions) and \vec{v} represents the unknown fluxes. To predict model fluxes, methods such as Flux Balance Analysis (FBA) and Flux Sampling (FS) are employed. FBA solves a linear programming problem to optimize the network for a specific objective function, which represents the cell’s metabolic goal, although assuming a single objective can be quite restrictive. Flux Sampling predicts fluxes by finding feasible solutions within the convex polytope defined by the constraints using Monte Carlo techniques, such as Coordinate Hit and Run with Rounding (CHRR), which samples the entire feasible region, or Corner-Based Sampling (CBS), which samples only the polytope’s boundary based on random objective coefficients. Techniques such as INTEGRATE [6], iMAT [15], and FASTCORE [16] have been developed to integrate transcriptomics data into GEMs within the CBM framework through Gene-Protein-Reaction (GPR) associations, thereby enhancing the characterization of cellular metabolism. GPRs are logical expressions (e.g., AND, OR rules) that capture the interplay between genetic information, the encoded proteins, and the biochemical reactions they catalyze. Novel methods like scFEA [7], based on artificial neural networks, aim to overcome the limitations of CBM models (e.g., linearity and steady-state assumptions) by directly inferring metabolic fluxes from transcriptomics data and GPRs without the need for a constraint-based framework.

Given the technical difficulties associated with directly measuring metabolic fluxes, validating integration methods has been limited to a restricted set of fluxes that can be compared to experimental data. Consequently, benchmarking such models remains an open challenge. The aim of this thesis is to establish an evaluation pipeline for integration methods to address the benchmarking problem and to leverage high-throughput data for characterizing metabolic phenotypes for further biological investigations. The analysis is based on the assumption that even if a specific enzyme is overexpressed in a cell, the absence of the associated metabolite, the reactant, reduces the overall reaction fluxes. Therefore, intracellular metabolomics can be treated as a proxy to identify metabolic similarities among cells. Moreover, it is the only omic that is not exploited to predict fluxomics by either INTEGRATE or scFEA. For these reasons, intracellular metabolomics was selected as the benchmark for comparing, through unsupervised learning techniques, the cancer phenotypes identified by INTEGRATE, and its possible technical variants, and scFEA. The former employs a constraint-based steady-state framework, while the latter uses a novel computational approach based on artificial neural networks. The second objective of the thesis is to identify optimal clustering solutions for each biological data source to assign cluster labels to each omic dataset, facilitating further investigations into biomarkers for these subpopulations. Life scientists can analyze biomarkers for each metabolic phenotype,

identifying patterns through clustering analyses based on metabolomics, transcriptomics, and fluxomics to derive useful biological insights.

In total, 513 different bulk cancer cell lines from the Cancer Cell Line Encyclopedia [5] were characterized by uncovering hidden metabolic subpopulations and evaluating the concordance among metabolomics, transcriptomics, and predicted fluxes generated by INTEGRATE and scFEA. For INTEGRATE, the RNA-seq matrix was used to create cell-specific metabolic models based on a generic core model called ENGRO2 [6]. Feasible fluxes were extracted either using Parsimonious-FBA - an evolution of classic FBA that aims to find the optimal solution among multiple solutions by minimizing total fluxes - or Flux Sampling (CHRR and CBS). Best practices defined by [1] and [17] were followed to avoid under-sampling and false discoveries in flux sampling. The development environment used to create the cell-specific models and predict fluxes derived from the INTEGRATE framework was based on the CONstraint-Based Reconstruction and Analysis Toolbox (COBRA toolbox) [18] and its Python implementation called COBRAPy [19]. In contrast to INTEGRATE, scFEA directly integrates gene expression into two neural networks without requiring a constraint-based model, predicting a single flux distribution per cell.

To robustly quantify the concordance amongst omics, an extensive grid search was conducted to find the optimal clustering hyperparameters across various algorithms: K-means [20], K-medoids [21], Agglomerative Clustering [22], HDBSCAN [22] and Leiden [23]. These algorithms were selected to cover as many fundamental clustering types as possible: centroid-based, hierarchical, density-based and graph-based. Internal evaluation metrics such as Silhouette Score, Calinski-Harabasz Index, and Density-Based Clustering Evaluation (DBCV) [24] were used to assess the intrinsic quality of the clustering solutions. External evaluation metrics, such as Normalized Mutual Information (NMI), were used to numerically assess the concordance among metabolic subpopulations identified by different omics datasets. Specifically, the optimal clustering configuration for each omic was determined by achieving the highest NMI with the metabolomics benchmark among the clustering results obtained through the grid search.

The transcriptomics matrix was preprocessed to remove technical noise using the MAGIC algorithm [8], which addresses the dropout phenomena where expressed genes are lost due to technical limitations. Originally intended for single-cell transcriptomics, it was found to be of extreme importance for bulk samples too.

The first chapter of this thesis discusses the theoretical foundations, including the role of metabolic models in disease analysis and the development of constraint-based models for predicting metabolic fluxes (e.g., Flux Balance Analysis and Flux Sampling). A review of integration frameworks for combining in-vitro omics data, such as transcriptomics, with mathematical models is also provided to outline the current state of the art. The second

chapter describes the CCLE dataset and the two benchmarked integration methods: INTEGRATE and scFEA. It also details the analysis methodologies, from preprocessing the transcriptomics matrix using MAGIC to the hyperparameter optimization for clustering algorithms. The results are then presented and discussed, leading to the conclusions chapter.

Chapter 1

Scientific background

1.1 Metabolic Networks

Metabolism encompasses all chemical reactions that sustain an organism's life. These reactions are catalyzed by proteins known as enzymes, which alter the reactants, or metabolites. When metabolic reactions within a cell are interconnected, they form metabolic pathways (an example of metabolic pathways are illustrated in Figure 1.1). Formally, a metabolic network is a bipartite graph where metabolites and reactions are the nodes of the network. A metabolite is connected to a reaction if the metabolite is a reactant or product of that reaction. Genome-scale metabolic models (GEMs) have various applications, including the development of strains for the production of chemicals and materials, drug targeting in pathogens, modelling interactions between multiple cells or organisms, and understanding human diseases [25]. Additionally, they are used to predict enzyme fluxes through optimization techniques such as flux balance analysis (FBA) [26].

Metabolic models can contain various Gene-Protein-Reaction associations (GPRs) which are logical expressions that describe the relationships between genes and the reactions they catalyze through the production of specific proteins called enzymes. These associations capture the complex interplay between genetic information, the proteins encoded by genes, and the biochemical reactions facilitated by these proteins [27]. These rules can be of three different kinds:

- **Single Gene:** A single gene is associated with a reaction. If this gene is knocked out, the reaction is blocked.
- **OR rule:** Multiple isoform genes are associated with a reaction. All genes must be knocked out to block the reaction.

$$gene_A \text{ OR } gene_B$$

- **AND rule:** Multiple genes are required for the reaction. Knocking out any one of these genes will block the reaction.

$$gene_A \text{ AND } gene_B$$

- **Complex Rule:** The reaction is associated with multiple genes using a combination of AND and OR rules. Knocking out one gene does not necessarily block the reaction.

$$gene_A \text{ AND } (gene_B \text{ OR } gene_C)$$

Figure 1.1: Energy production pathways of a human cell. Image taken from [28].

1.2 Linear programming

Linear programming (LP) is a mathematical approach for solving optimization problems. It is based on a mathematical model that describes the real-world problem through linear functions. The distribution of limited resources among competing activities remains the most common application area, but numerous other applications exist. One of the most efficient and effective procedures, even for large-scale problems, is known as the simplex method [29]. The standard form of an LP problem involves selecting the values of the variables x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n in order to maximize or minimize the function $Z = c_1x_1 + c_2x_2 + \dots + c_nx_n$ referred to as the objective function. Each variable x_i contributes to the final value of Z according to the weight expressed by the coefficient c_i . The constraints of the model are divided into functional constraints and non-negativity constraints.

$$\begin{aligned} a_{1,1}x_1 + a_{1,2}x_2 + \dots + a_{1,n}x_n &\leq b_1 \\ a_{2,1}x_1 + a_{2,2}x_2 + \dots + a_{2,n}x_n &\leq b_2 \\ &\dots \\ a_{m,1}x_1 + a_{m,2}x_2 + \dots + a_{m,n}x_n &\leq b_m \end{aligned} \tag{1.1}$$

and

$$x_1 \geq 0, x_2 \geq 0, \dots, x_n \geq 0$$

The objective is to identify the optimal solution, if it exists, that satisfies all the constraints of the model, thus an optimal and feasible solution. The search area containing the solution is called the feasible region and is defined by the intersection of all the constraints (as schematized in Figure 1.2). When the problem is defined in more than three dimensions, the feasible region is called a polytope, which is the N-dimensional analog of a plane in two dimensions or a polyhedron in three-dimensional space. Specifically, optimal solutions are found on the boundary of the feasible region, not within the entire search space. The boundary equation for any constraint is obtained by replacing the symbols \leq or \geq with the equal sign. Along the boundary are the feasible vertices, i.e., solutions of a system of m equations involving the variables $x_1 \dots x_n$. Not all vertices are feasible, which occurs when at least one constraint is not satisfied at the point. Another relevant geometric component in the problem is the edge: "An edge of the feasible region is a line segment consisting of feasible points that lie at the intersection of the boundaries of $m - 1$ constraints, whose endpoints lie on the boundary of an additional constraint [...]. Two feasible vertices are adjacent if the segment connecting them is an edge of the feasible region. From each vertex, n edges are generated, each leading to one of the n adjacent vertices" [29]. Two fundamental properties of vertices clarify why optimal solutions are found exclusively along the boundary:

1. Fundamental theorem of linear programming: if there is a single optimal solution, then it is a vertex. If there are multiple optimal solutions and the feasible region is bounded, then at least two optimal solutions are adjacent feasible vertices.
2. If a feasible vertex has no better adjacent vertices in terms of Z , then no better vertices exist. Assuming the problem has at least one optimal solution, then the vertex with this characteristic is an optimal solution. This is motivated by the convexity of the feasible region, which does not allow indentations that would lead to better adjacent vertices.

By searching for the optimal points among the vertices of the feasible region, the number of solutions to be examined is significantly reduced, becoming finite in number, unlike the infinite feasible solutions on the boundary. In fact, the simplex method explores the boundary by moving from one vertex to another, based on the direction of the greatest increase in the objective function Z .

Figure 1.2: Example of constraint boundaries and vertices for an LP problem with variables x and y .

1.3 Constraint-based modelling

1.3.1 FBA

Flux Balance Analysis (FBA) is a widely used linear optimization method for analyzing genome-scale metabolic models. These networks encompass all the metabolic reactions of an organism and the genes encoding the corresponding enzymes [26]. The objective of FBA is to calculate the rates, or fluxes, of each reaction in the network by extracting the information encoded within the model. To achieve this, it is necessary to translate the model into a mathematical structure: the stoichiometric matrix S (see step 2 in Figure 1.3). The matrix has dimensions $m \times r$, where m is the number of metabolites and r is the number of reactions. Each column represents a reaction and contains the stoichiometric coefficients of the participating metabolites [17]. The fluxes throughout the entire model are represented by a vector \vec{v} , and the set of \vec{v} such that $S\vec{v} = \vec{0}$, i.e., the null space of the matrix, expresses all feasible fluxes of the model. This representation imposes mass balance constraints on the reaction fluxes, assuming a steady state, which refers to the particular state in which metabolite concentrations are constant, balancing production and consumption.

Given the solution space, i.e. a polytope identified by the imposed constraints, FBA defines an optimization problem on the fluxes to study the model's behavior under a specific objective function. FBA aims to maximize or minimize the objective function $Z = \vec{c}^T \vec{v}$, where \vec{c} is a weight vector indicating how much a reaction should contribute to the calculation of Z . Often, the objective function corresponds to a single flux to be optimized, \vec{v}_i , resulting in the following linear programming problem:

$$\begin{aligned} \max / \min \quad & \vec{v}_i & (1.2) \\ S \cdot \vec{v} &= \vec{0} \\ \vec{v}_L &\leq \vec{v} \leq \vec{v}_U, \end{aligned}$$

where \vec{v}_L and \vec{v}_U represent the lower and upper bounds for the model fluxes. FBA also allows for the comparison of different experimental conditions with varying model constraints. FBA provides a single solution to the optimization problem by visiting the vertices of the feasible region (linear programming), but alternative solutions may exist.

1.3.2 pFBA

Parsimonious Flux Balance Analysis (pFBA) is an extension of standard FBA that incorporates an additional objective: minimizing the total flux through the network. While FBA determines the optimal flux distribution to maximize or minimize a given objective function, such as biomass production, it often results in multiple equally optimal solutions due to the redundancy

and flexibility inherent in metabolic networks. pFBA addresses this by introducing the principle of parsimony, which assumes that biological systems are likely to minimize the use of resources, leading to the selection of a solution that requires the least overall enzyme usage. The pFBA method operates in two main steps: FBA Optimization and Secondary Optimization for Parsimony. In the first step, standard FBA is performed to determine the maximum or minimum value of the objective function, such as the biomass production rate Z_{max} :

$$\begin{aligned} \max Z &= \vec{c}^T \vec{v} \\ S \cdot \vec{v} &= \vec{0} \\ \vec{v}_L &\leq \vec{v} \leq \vec{v}_U, \end{aligned} \tag{1.3}$$

where S is the stoichiometric matrix, \vec{v} is the flux vector, and \vec{c} is the coefficient vector for the objective function. Once the optimal value Z_{max} is determined, a secondary optimization is performed to minimize the total flux through the network while still achieving the objective value found in the first step:

$$\begin{aligned} \min \sum_i |v_i| \\ S \cdot \vec{v} &= \vec{0} \\ \vec{v}_L &\leq \vec{v} \leq \vec{v}_U \\ \vec{c}^T \vec{v} &= Z_{max}, \end{aligned} \tag{1.4}$$

where the objective is to minimize the sum of absolute flux values, ensuring that the solution is parsimonious by reducing the overall flux through the network. By incorporating this secondary optimization, pFBA not only finds a feasible solution but also ensures that the solution is biologically plausible, reflecting the likely preference of organisms to minimize metabolic costs.

1.3.3 FVA

The Flux Variability Analysis (FVA) is used to calculate the optimality ranges of each flux, defining their limits. FVA solves the following two optimization problems, one of minimization and one of maximization, for each desired flux v_j , with $j = 1, \dots, r$:

$$\begin{aligned} \max / \min v_j \\ S \cdot \vec{v} &= \vec{0} \\ \vec{v}_L &\leq \vec{v} \leq \vec{v}_U \\ \vec{v}_j &\geq \gamma Z_0, \end{aligned} \tag{1.5}$$

where Z_0 is an optimal solution for 1.2 and γ is the parameter used for performing FVA referring to a suboptimal ($0 \leq \gamma < 1$) or optimal ($\gamma = 1$) state.

1) GEM definition

2) Mathematical representation of reactions and metabolites through the system of stoichiometric equations

3) Objective function Z

$$Z = c^T v$$

4) Optimization problem resolution

Figure 1.3: The steps of FBA.

1.3.4 Sensitivity analysis

Mathematical models, such as constraint-based metabolic networks, can be highly complex, making the relationships between inputs and outputs difficult to discern. Consequently, sensitivity analysis is employed in the context of metabolic models to assess the influence of alterations in constraints on a predefined output feature. For instance, the deletion, or knockout, of a model reaction from the stoichiometric matrix S is equivalent to setting its upper bound to zero. By doing this, it becomes possible to analyze the effect of such deletions by performing Flux Balance Analysis (FBA) using a key reaction, such as Biomass, as the objective function. The sensitivity coefficient of reaction j indicates the fraction of preserved Biomass flux after the deletion of reaction j and it is defined as follows:

$$\text{Sensitivity}_j = \frac{Z_j^{KO}}{Z_{Biomass}} \quad (1.6)$$

where Z_j^{KO} is the Biomass optimized flux after the deletion of reaction j and $Z_{Biomass}$ is the Biomass optimized flux of the original model. This procedure is repeated for all model reactions, resulting in an array of sensitivity coefficients of length r , where r represents the number of model reactions.

1.4 Flux Sampling

Flux Balance Analysis (FBA) imposes an objective function to explore metabolic models, which introduces a bias because it assumes a specific cellular goal. For example, studying how a bacterium's metabolism changes under high temperature versus normal conditions requires identifying an objective to optimize, which is often unknown and can lead to inaccurate conclusions if chosen incorrectly. On the other hand, FVA returns only the range of each flux, while it does not provide specific flux distributions. Flux sampling (FS) is used to uniformly sample the entire feasible region, unlike FBA which focuses on a single vertex, creating a set of feasible solutions. This sampling provides a finite representation of the metabolic network, allowing the extraction of key insights about the entire model. As compared to FVA and FBA, FS also offers information on the range and probability distributions of fluxes.

There are two formulations for each metabolic model in the context of flux sampling: deterministic, used in this thesis, and stochastic. The deterministic approach follows FBA, applying steady-state constraints, while the stochastic formulation relaxes these constraints, allowing for measurement errors. Figure 1.4 shows how these methods differ in sampling fluxes v_1 and v_2 . In the deterministic formulation (panels a and b), sampling v_1 determines v_2 's values, producing probability distribution functions (pdf) that reflect their mass points. The stochastic approach (panels c and d) introduces measurement uncertainty in v_1 , leading to different distributions (panel c). Adding stoichiometric constraint relaxations (panel d) provides a more realistic stochastic metabolism model, avoiding strong steady-state assumptions. Considering measurement uncertainty and stoichiometric relaxations results in a broader pdf and a feasible region (polytope) that is not necessarily convex.

Deterministic formulation

Stochastic formulation

Figure 1.4: Solution space and pdfs associated with sampling. (a): deterministic formulation without sampling. (b): deterministic approach with sampling. (c): stochastic approach with uncertainty in v_1 . (d): stochastic approach with additional stoichiometric relaxation [30].

The quality of sampling affects conclusions, making the choice of flux sampling algorithm crucial, whether deterministic or stochastic (e.g., Gibbs sampler [31], not covered here). Figure 1.5 shows two examples of sampling the same feasible region. In the left panel, the sampling is ineffective, limited to one area, while the right panel shows well-representative sampling of the entire model.

Figure 1.5: Difference between ineffective sampling of the polytope (left panel) and well-representative sampling (right panel).

Sampling algorithms are used in flux sampling to uniformly sample the polytope defined by model constraints, creating a sequence of points called a chain. This thesis used the Coordinate Hit-and-Run with Rounding (CHRR) to sample the entire feasible region and the Corner-Base Sampling (CBS) to sample the vertices of the polytope. CHRR is based on Markov chains, necessitating an introduction to their fundamental properties.

1.4.1 Markov Chains

A Markov chain X is a finite-time stochastic process $\{X_0, X_1, \dots\}$ characterized by the Markov property, or memorylessness:

$$P(X_t \in A | X_0, X_1, \dots, X_{t-1}) = P(X_t \in A | X_{t-1}), \quad (1.7)$$

where A is any set containing states. This equation defines the dependence of state X_t only on X_{t-1} , not on past states. In this thesis, all possible states of the chain belong to R^n , where n is the number of fluxes in the model. Thus, it is a general, non-discrete state space. All presented concepts will pertain to the discrete formulation, with extensions to general spaces requiring only technical adjustments [32].

Given the current state of the chain, there is a probability distribution for the next state. If there are n possible states, the transition matrix \mathbf{P} , of dimensions $n \cdot n$, fully describes the chain by indexing various states in rows

and columns. The value $\mathbf{P}(x, y)$ represents the probability of transitioning to y at time $t + 1$ from x at time t . The matrix \mathbf{P} is stochastic because each row contains positive values summing to one, representing a probability distribution in R^n . The most important concept, especially for the CHRR algorithm, is the stationary distribution π . A distribution π is stationary for a Markov chain \mathbf{P} if $\pi\mathbf{P} = \pi$. Specifically, if the stationary distribution of X_t is π , it will be the same for X_{t+1} , remaining unchanged over time. A Markov chain converges to the stationary distribution if it is:

- **Irreducible:** for all states x and y , there exists $t \geq 0$ such that $P^t(x, y) > 0$.
- **Aperiodic:** the chain does not periodically oscillate between state groups. Let $\tau(x) = \{t \geq 1 : P^t(x, x) > 0\}$ be the set of times for the chain to return to x . The period of state x is the greatest common divisor of $\tau(x)$. The chain is aperiodic if for every state x , $\gcd \tau(x) = 1$.

Irreducibility also ensures the uniqueness of the stationary distribution π , which is representative of all reachable states, i.e., the entire polytope in our case, because it remains unchanged over time regardless of new points added.

1.4.2 Internal Sampling of the Polytope

Hit and Run (HR)

The first approach for sampling the feasible region is based on the Hit and Run (HR) algorithm. It follows the Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) methodology, characterized by Markov chains where points are generated through a random process. The Markov property is respected, meaning the next sampled point depends only on the last point added to the chain, the current state, and not on any previous states. HR collects samples from an N -dimensional convex space called P , the polytope generated by the stoichiometric matrix, arbitrarily identifying the point $v_0 \in P$ as the first state of the chain (see Figure 1.6). Additionally, the variable i is initialized as an iteration counter, defined as follows:

1. Choose an arbitrary direction Θ^i from a uniform distribution limited by the unit sphere in R^N .
2. Find the minimum λ_{min} and the maximum λ_{max} such that $v_i + \lambda_{min}\Theta^i \in P$ and $v_i + \lambda_{max}\Theta^i \in P$.
3. Randomly choose the step size λ_i within the interval $[\lambda_{min}, \lambda_{max}]$.
4. Generate the new sample $v_{i+1} = v_i + \Theta^i\lambda_i$ such that $v_{i+1} \in P$.

HR can be efficient even in high-dimensional polytopes, but despite the convergence to the target distribution being ensured by the Markov property, irreducibility, and aperiodicity of the chains, it is generally not used due to the phenomenon of slow mixing. This occurs when, during exploration, one approaches corners or narrow regions of the polytope. Consequently, the calculated step sizes are short, leading to the generation of very similar samples, risking entrapment in the sector for many iterations.

There is a parameter, called the seed, used by the algorithm to generate all the random values used in the various iterations. Indeed, the same seed value results in identical chains. This parameter is commonly included in all algorithms with a stochastic component.

Figure 1.6: An example of polytope P sampling using the HR algorithm.

Coordinate Hit-and-Run with Rounding (CHRR)

ACHR [33] was developed to address the slow mixing issue of the HR algorithm. The goal is to identify optimal directions to utilize larger step sizes. Setting M as the number of points called warm-up points, $M \geq N$ iterations are performed as defined by HR. During the first iteration, a point $v_0 \in P$ is determined as the first element of the chain, and the artificial center $\hat{c} = v_0$ is initialized. After the warm-up phase, the actual sampling begins:

1. Choose a number a uniformly distributed in the interval of integers $[0, i]$ and calculate the direction $\Theta^i = \frac{v_a - \hat{c}}{\|v_i - \hat{c}\|}$.
2. Determine the step size λ_i as in HR.
3. Generate the new sample $v_{i+1} = v_i + \Theta^i \lambda_i$.
4. Update the estimated center $\hat{c} = \frac{i\hat{c} + v_i}{i+1}$.

Samples generated by ACHR depend on all the points already present in the chain, which makes the algorithm non-Markovian. Without the Markov property, convergence to the stationary distribution π is not guaranteed. Additionally, ACHR exhibits slow sampling in high-dimensional polytopes. There is an additional parameter K , called the thinning value, which reduces the autocorrelation of samples by adding points to the chain only every K iterations.

As previously described, the shape of the polytope P can negatively affect the HR process (ill-conditioning). To address this issue, CHRR [34] employs a two-phase strategy: rounding and sampling. The rounding phase involves two operations:

1. Construct an ellipsoid of maximum volume inscribed within the polytope P .
2. Round P by transforming the inscribed ellipsoid into a unit sphere.

The sampling phase is executed using the coordinate hit-and-run (CHR) algorithm [35], a variant of HR capable of sampling the rounded polytope. At each CHR iteration, the direction Θ^i is randomly determined within the space, respecting the Markov property. Finally, it is necessary to transform the coordinates of the sampled points in the rounded polytope back to their original positions in P . Unlike ACHR, CHRR guarantees convergence to the target distribution because it is based on the CHR algorithm, which belongs to the MCMC methods family. The thinning parameter is also present in this case.

1.4.3 Corner-Based Sampling (CBS)

The algorithms presented so far sample the entire feasible region, but there is a second approach in the realm of flux sampling based on optimizing fluxes through random objective functions [36]. Each sample is the result of an optimization process, thus representing a vertex of the feasible region rather than a point within it. In this thesis, the CBS algorithm was implemented as follows [1]:

1. Randomly choose which reactions take part in the objective function Z .
2. Random weights w_i are uniformly drawn from the interval $[-1, 1]$.
3. The weights are then divided by the maximal flux obtained using Flux Variability Analysis (FVA).
4. Finally, each objective function is either maximized or minimized with equal probability 0.5.

At the end of the initialization procedure, all the previously calculated parameters are used to perform S iterations of the following steps, with S being the desired number of samples.

In models of relatively low dimensions, such as ENGRO2, CBS requires only a few samples to identify all the vertices of the polytope, leading to chains of flow solutions that are very similar to each other or duplicates, in the case of sufficient rounding. For flux sampling algorithms based on MCMC methods, such as CHRR it can be useful to sample the model multiple times, with different seeds, increasing the quantity of collected points each time. This allows for analyzing the different behaviors of the algorithm in relation to the number of sampled points. However, concerning CBS, the absence of the concept of a chain, due to the purely stochastic process of the algorithm, renders the increase in the cardinality of sampling meaningless. For instance, performing 21 samplings of 1000 points each, for a total of 21000 samples, is not different from performing samplings from 1,000 to 6,000 points with a step of 1000, again totaling 21000 samples. There is no difference because CBS always behaves the same regardless of the collected samples and their number. This is not the case for the CHRR because the chains depend on at least one past state, so the sampling cardinality can influence the behavior of the algorithm.

1.4.4 False discoveries and sampling best practises

HR sampling algorithms can encounter convergence issues, such as insufficient sampling to fully characterize the solution space or exploration limited to a subset of the entire solution space. Consequently, when conducting differential metabolic flux analysis, comparing flux distributions from two patient-specific or tissue-specific models may lead to false discoveries if this bias is not properly addressed [17]. For instance, rejecting the null hypothesis that two reactions have identical metabolic flux (type I error) in the two models could occur due to sampling bias, as shown by Figure 1.7. Recent findings suggested that CHRR is the most promising Monte Carlo sampling algorithm. Additionally, among the potential configurations of MC sampling parameters, employing a high thinning value is crucial for reducing the FDR [1].

1.4.5 Samples statistics

The post-processing of flux distributions obtained through flux sampling can represent a computational challenge because of the high dimensionality of the feature space and the large sample size required to minimize the risk of false discoveries. For these reasons, it is possible to apply statistical analyses to summarize the flux distributions. For a generic metabolic model, the resulting matrix containing samples of size $n \times m$ (where m is the number of

Figure 1.7: Example of low quality sampling of the same feasible region that leads to false discoveries. Image taken from [1].

reactions and n is the sample size) is summarized to a single vector of size m , thereby reducing the dataset to just one unique sample. The following statistics can be used for this purpose:

- **Mean:**

$$\mu_j = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_{ij} \quad (1.8)$$

where μ_j is the average flux for reaction j across all samples. The average is sensible to outliers, hence it could be biased by extreme values that are not necessarily well representative of the original distribution.

- **Median** The median \tilde{x} of x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n is given by:

$$\tilde{x} = \begin{cases} x_{(\frac{n+1}{2})} & \text{if } n \text{ is odd} \\ \frac{x_{(\frac{n}{2})} + x_{(\frac{n}{2}+1)}}{2} & \text{if } n \text{ is even} \end{cases} \quad (1.9)$$

It can give a robust indication of the central flux values.

- **Mode:** The mode can capture the most frequent, hence the real potential cell objective, flux distribution amongst all samples. It is originally intended for categorical or discrete data, but thanks to the Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) method, it is extensible to continuous data too. KDE is a non-parametric way to estimate the probability density function of a continuous random variable. It is used to create a smooth estimate of the distribution of sample data:

$$\hat{f}(x) = \frac{1}{nh} \sum_{i=1}^n K\left(\frac{x - x_i}{h}\right) \quad (1.10)$$

Where:

- $\hat{f}(x)$ is the estimated density at point x .
- n is the number of data points.
- h is the bandwidth, a parameter that controls the smoothness of the density estimate.
- K is the kernel function, which determines the shape of the distribution placed at each data point x_i

A Common choice for the kernel function K is the Gaussian kernel:

$$K(u) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}u^2} \quad (1.11)$$

The mode of a continuous distribution is the point where the density function reaches its maximum value. In the context of Kernel Density Estimation (KDE), the mode can be found by identifying the maximum value of the estimated density function $\hat{f}(x)$. For each reaction j , the mode can be computed over the reaction distribution across samples by estimating the KDE and identifying the flux solution Mode_j with the highest density.

Moreover, correlation analysis can be utilized to examine the relationship between the sampled reactions and a target reaction, such as Biomass, which represents a primary cellular objective. Specifically, given n samples over r different reactions, the Spearman correlation coefficient is computed between each reaction and a predefined proxy reaction, usually Biomass. The Spearman correlation coefficient ρ between two variables X and Y is calculated as follows:

$$\rho = 1 - \frac{6 \sum_{i=1}^n d_i^2}{n(n^2 - 1)} \quad (1.12)$$

where d_i is the difference between the ranks of corresponding values of X and Y . This analysis helps in understanding the degree of monotonic relationship between each reaction and the target reaction, providing insights into the impact of each reaction on the cellular objective. The Spearman correlation coefficient is particularly advantageous in this context because it assesses monotonic relationships rather than strictly linear relationships, as is the case with the Pearson correlation coefficient. This makes it more robust to outliers and non-linear distributions of data, which are often encountered in metabolic network models. Consequently, Spearman's method provides a more reliable measure of the association between reactions and the core objective in complex biological systems.

1.5 Omics data integration

Effective stratification of cancer patients based on their molecular profiles is a critical challenge due to the altered and heterogeneous nature of cancer metabolism. Metabolism, integral to all cellular processes, reflects the physiological and pathological state of a cell or organism [9]. Transcriptomics, proteomics, and metabolomics offer snapshots of transcripts, enzyme levels, and metabolites under specific conditions. Gene expression sets the upper limit of metabolic enzymes, while metabolites interact with these enzymes to auto-regulate metabolism. More in depth, metabolomics can be further categorized into two main subgroups:

- **Intracellular Metabolomics:** This focuses on the metabolites found within cells. It involves analyzing the small molecules produced by cellular processes to understand the metabolic activities and pathways within the cell. Intracellular metabolomics provides insights into the cell's physiological state, biochemical reactions, and how cells respond to various stimuli or stressors.
- **Extracellular Metabolomics:** This examines the metabolites present in the cell culture spent media and how the cell exchanges metabolites with the external environment. It aims to understand how cells interact with their environment and how metabolites are secreted or exchanged between cells. Extracellular metabolomics is essential for studying systemic metabolic responses and can provide valuable information for biomarker discovery, disease diagnosis, and monitoring of metabolic disorders.

On the other hand, transcriptomics methods such as RNA sequencing (RNA-seq) [12] aim at revealing the presence and quantity of RNA molecule in a biological sample to gain insights about the expression level of specific genes and dependent proteins which act as enzymes into the cell metabolism.

Current research on human metabolism usually relies on genome-wide reconstructions of metabolic networks, like Recon3D [10], or core models focused on specific reaction sets, like ENGRO2 [6]. Then, constraint-based modeling techniques such as Flux Balance Analysis (FBA) are used to predict metabolic fluxes. These predictive methods assume a steady-state where metabolite concentrations are balanced between production and consumption. Constraint-based steady-state models are considered as valuable framework for predicting metabolic fluxes using high-throughput omics data [37]. Direct determination of metabolic fluxes through labelled substrates (metabolites) is technically challenging [2] and they are only partially influenced by gene/enzyme expression variations. For this reason, flux prediction methods, such as constraint-based models, are preferred. In general, at least three kind of regulations can be responsible for fluxes variations:

- **Transcriptional control:** Variations in the flux through the reaction are mainly influenced by changes in the enzyme (E) abundance, driven by gene expression. This occurs when the substrate (S) is in large excess, and the enzyme is saturated (S concentration much higher than K_m). In this scenario, changes in substrate concentration do not significantly affect the flux, as long as S remains in excess after the changes in its or the enzyme's abundance. There are also two additional controls for enzyme production: post-transcriptional and post-translational controls. Post-transcriptional control regulates the processing and stability of mRNA, while post-translational control involves the modification and activation of enzymes after they are synthesized.
- **Metabolic control:** Variations in the flux through the reaction are primarily controlled by changes in the substrate (S) abundance. This is typical when the enzyme (E) is in large excess (S concentration is below or near K_m). Here, the flux is not significantly impacted by changes in enzyme abundance due to gene expression, provided the enzyme remains in excess after the variations in its or the substrate's abundance.
- **Combined metabolic and transcriptional control:** Flux variations are driven by simultaneous changes in both substrate (S) and enzyme (E) abundance. This occurs when the enzyme is in moderate excess over the substrate (S concentration slightly above K_m), and a significant increase in S abundance saturates the enzyme. An increase in S alone can enhance the flux, but a concurrent rise in enzyme levels can further augment it.

Conversely, while transcriptomics and metabolomics datasets are increasingly being generated [38], these datasets alone do not allow for precise characterization of the regulatory mechanisms governing metabolism unless properly integrated. They can be integrated within metabolic models, for example by using the constraint-based paradigm, or they can be analyzed independently of these models.

When analyzed outside model-based techniques, the integration of transcriptomics and metabolomics data has predominantly been limited to two main approaches:

- **Gene-Metabolite Correlation Analysis:** This approach involves identifying correlations between gene expression levels and metabolite concentrations.
- **Pathway Enrichment Analysis:** This method involves mapping genes and metabolites to known metabolic pathways and determining which pathways are significantly enriched.

On the other hand, transcriptomics and metabolomics data can be incorporated into constraint-based frameworks as additional constraints on the network. For example, REMI (Relative Expression and Metabolomic Integrations) [39] allows for gene-expression, metabolite abundance and thermodynamic data to be integrated into a single constraint-based framework, enhancing the accuracy of flux predictions. However, integrating metabolomics data to predict fluxes requires strong assumptions about the mathematical relationships between metabolites and fluxes. Often, a linear relationship is assumed, which may not always hold true, limiting the accuracy and applicability of the predictions [6].

A plethora of methods have been developed to integrate RNA-seq profiles into constraint-based metabolic models [40] (see Table 1.1). They integrate transcriptomics by imposing new model constraints based on Gene-Protein-Reaction (GPR) associations [40]. Examples include iMAT [15], GIMME [41], and INTEGRATE [6]. The iMAT framework is used to extract context specific constraint-based models using gene expression data by finding the optimal trade-off between including high-expression reactions and removing low-expression reactions. Similarly, GIMME minimizes the usage of low-expression reactions while keeping the objective function value (e.g. biomass) above a certain threshold. INTEGRATE (Model-based multi-omics data INTEGRAtion to characterize multi-level metabolic regulation) is a computational framework intended to precisely characterize the landscape of metabolic regulation in various biological samples, starting from metabolomics and transcriptomics data. First, it computes the Reaction Activity Score (RAS) for each model reaction based on RNA-seq and GPRs, hence transcriptional regulation only. Then, RAS and cell medium data are used to define cell-specific constraints over a generic constraint-based metabolic model. Finally, intracellular metabolomic is used to compute the two main output features: a list containing fluxes that vary across cells consistently with both metabolic and transcriptional regulation and a list having fluxes that vary consistently with metabolic regulation only. iMAT, GIMME and INTEGRATE allow obtaining cell-specific constraint-based models that can be successively analyzed through techniques such as Flux Balance Analysis (FBA) and Flux Sampling (FS).

Table 1.1: RNA-seq integration frameworks.

Name	Publication year	Reference
INTEGRATE	2022	[6]
scFEA	2021	[7]
iMAT	2010	[15]
GIMME	2008	[41]

scFEA (single-cell flux estimation analysis) is a novel graph neural network method that bypasses the traditional constraint-based framework. It addresses two main limitations of previously established methods such as INTEGRATE and iMAT. Firstly, mass balance constraints may not be appropriate for diseases with significant metabolite imbalances, such as cancer. Secondly, gene expression is not directly used to model cellular fluxes, but imposed as new constraints on the model to guide the search for solutions. scFEA is designed to estimate cell-specific metabolic fluxes using single-cell RNA-seq data. It leverages a reorganized human metabolic map into focused metabolic modules and integrates a probabilistic model to apply flux balance constraints on scRNA-seq data. Additionally, a novel GNN-based optimization solver is utilized to capture the non-linear dependencies between gene expressions and reaction rates through multi-layer neural networks. This approach enables the direct prediction of cell-specific flux distributions without the need for Flux Balance Analysis (FBA) or Flux Sampling (FS).

In general, the evaluation of integration frameworks performance is often constrained by the benchmarking issue. Indeed, the technical challenges in directly measuring metabolic fluxes hinder the comparison between predicted and actual fluxes.

Chapter 2

Methods

2.1 Cancer Cell Line Encyclopedia

The Cancer Cell Line Encyclopedia (CCLE) [5] Project is a comprehensive and collaborative effort aimed at cataloging and analyzing the genetic and pharmacological characteristics of cancer cell lines. Initiated by the Broad Institute and Novartis, the project aims to provide a resource for the scientific community to facilitate cancer research and drug development.

In this thesis, bulk transcriptomics (RNA-seq [12]) and intracellular metabolomics data from 512 different cancer cell lines were downloaded from CCLE. Bulk samples differ from single-cell RNA-seq (scRNA-seq) in that gene expression is measured over a collection of cells from the same tissue (bulk) rather than from individual cancer cells. This technique overcomes many of the technical challenges associated with scRNA-seq experiments, where noise can significantly impact data quality due to the reduced sample size.

All the tumor samples were cultured in the same RPMI 1640 medium [42], ensuring a consistent nutrient environment (extra-cellular metabolomics). The cancer cell lines originate from various primary sites, as illustrated in Figure 2.2, with over 25% of the tumors affecting hematopoietic and lymphoid tissues (e.g., blood, bone marrow, lymph, and lymphatic system). In terms of pathology, 68.55% of cells are from primary sites, while the remaining are metastatic. The most common histological class is carcinoma (malignant epithelial tumor), comprising more than 60% of the samples. Moreover, 56.92% of the samples are from male patients. The age of patients ranges from 1 to over 80 years, with a median age of around 55 years (see 2.1).

Figure 2.1: Age and gender boxplots of the analysed cell lines.

Figure 2.2: Explorative analysis of the analysed cancer bulk samples. A) Primary sites relative frequencies. B) Histologies relative frequencies.

2.2 ENGRO 2

The human metabolic network ENGRO2 was used to integrate the cell transcriptomics to better characterize metabolic fluxes. It is the evolution of the ENGRO1 model [43] and it focuses on central carbon metabolism and essential amino acid metabolism. This network was recently used to create the integration framework, INTEGRATE [6]. ENGRO2 is characterized by 462 reactions (394 irreversible and 67 reversible) 391 metabolites, and 495 genes. It is formed by three metabolic compartments which contain a unique set of enzymes and conditions optimized for particular biochemical reactions: extracellular, cytosol and mitochondrion. The medium of a model refers to the set of external conditions and nutrients available to the system being modelled. It specifies which metabolites can be transported into and out of the system, essentially defining the environment in which the metabolic network operates. This is crucial for simulating realistic biological conditions and understanding how changes in the external environment affect cellular metabolism. ENGRO2 medium contains 36 elements:

- 20 amino acids plus cystine
- Glucose and galactose
- Cholesterol and palmitic acid
- Pyruvate, lactate
- Putrescine
- Folic acid (only vitamin present)
- Thymidine
- Oxygen (essential)
- Phosphorus
- Hydrogen, oxygen and water
- Tetrahydrobiopterin (essential for synthesising tyrosine from phen)

Of these, the following are essential for cell growth:

- the nine essential amino acids plus arginine
- the oxygen.
- the phosphate

The selected 512 cancer bulk samples were cultivated with the same medium called RPMI 1640 [42]. Over a total of 462 reaction, ENGRO2 has the following GPRs:

- 196 reactions with a single associated gene
- 16 reactions with AND rules
- 96 reactions with OR rules
- 35 reactions with complex rules
- 114 reactions without associated genes

2.3 Data integration

2.3.1 Cell-specific metabolic models

INTEGRATE (Model-based multi-omics data INTEGRATION to characterize multi-level metabolic regulation) is a computational framework intended to precisely characterize the landscape of metabolic regulation in various biological samples, starting from metabolomics and transcriptomics data. It integrates transcriptomics data into a constraint-based steady-state model to predict fluxomics and allows for correlation analysis between transcriptomics and metabolomics. It applies three types of constraints:

1. **Medium/nutrient availability constraints:** The network can only exploit the supplied metabolites present in the growth medium. This can influence the model uptake upper-bounds.
2. **Extracellular fluxes:** The ratio between consumed and produced metabolites of each single reaction can be estimated and constrained.
3. **RNA-seq transcriptomics constraints:** For each reaction, the Reaction Activity Score is computed based on RNA-seq and GPRs.

In this thesis, the INTEGRATE pipeline was applied to generate new cell-specific metabolic models by integrating transcriptomics data through the computation of the Reaction Activity Score (RAS). This approach permitted the execution of flux optimization techniques, such as Flux Balance Analysis (FBA) and Flux Variability Analysis (FVA), along with flux sampling algorithms, including Coordinate Hit-and-Run with Rounding (CHRR) and Constraint-Based Sampling (CBS), across different cell profiles. The development environment used to create the cell-specific models and predict fluxes derived from the INTEGRATE framework was based on the COntstraint-Based Reconstruction and Analysis Toolbox (COBRA toolbox) [18] and its Python implementation called COBRAPy [19]. Only INTEGRATE constraints based on RNA-seq and medium were used because exchange fluxes ratio were not available. Moreover, only the data integration step of the INTEGRATE pipeline was applied to create cell-specific models characterized by gene expression level (the downstream analysis to identify the level of

regulation of fluxes using intracellular metabolomics is beyond the scope of this work). All the cells considered in the analysis shared the very same growth medium, hence nutrient availability constraints are shared amongst all models. Consequentially, type 1 constraints set the theoretically maximum fluxes upper-bound, while RNA-seq data constraints define the effective bounds for a given reaction and cell. RNA-seq data integration defines a new cell-specific metabolic model tailored specifically for each individual cell (see Figure 2.3).

The Reaction Activity Score (RAS) is employed to integrate RNA-seq datasets with GPR rules. The RAS assumes additive contributions from enzyme isoforms to reaction activity, with the least expressed enzyme subunit being the limiting factor. For each cell line c in the set C of cell lines, for each sample ξ , and for each reaction r , the RAS $\text{RAS}_{c,r,\xi}$ is calculated by resolving the corresponding logical expression. Specifically, for genes connected by an AND operator, the minimum transcript level is taken:

$$\text{RAS}_{c,r,\xi} = \min\{T_{g,c} : g \in G_r\} \quad (2.1)$$

where G_r denotes the set of genes encoding the subunits of the enzyme catalyzing reaction r . For genes connected by an OR operator, the sum of their values is taken:

$$\text{RAS}_{c,r,\xi} = \sum T_{g,c} : g \in G_r \quad (2.2)$$

In scenarios involving both AND and OR operators, their standard precedence is followed. The reaction activity score for each cell line is then averaged over the samples:

$$\text{RAS}_{c,r} = \langle \text{RAS}_{c,r,\xi} \rangle_{\xi} \quad (2.3)$$

Subsequently, the scores are normalized against the maximum RAS of all cell lines:

$$\overline{\text{RAS}}_{c,r} = \frac{\text{RAS}_{c,r}}{\max\{\text{RAS}_{c,r}\}_c} \quad (2.4)$$

If the RAS is zero for all cell lines, the normalized score is also set to zero. For reactions not associated with a GPR, the RAS is set to 1.

The RAS and type 1 constraints of the 513 bulk samples were integrated, as done by [6], into the constraint-based steady-state ENGRO2 model. Given a stoichiometric matrix S of dimensions $M \times N$, where M represents metabolites and N represents reactions, along with a flux vector v , the steady state

assumption dictates that $S \cdot v = 0$. This implies that the null space of the matrix S corresponds to the set of flux vectors v that satisfy the steady state condition. The space of feasible fluxes can be constrained using convex half-planes. These half-planes are defined by the vectors v_L and v_U , which represent the lower and upper bounds, respectively, for the components of the flux vector v . Thus, the bounds restrict the flux values to ensure they remain within biologically plausible limits. In mathematical terms:

- The steady state condition is given by:

$$S \cdot v = 0$$

- The flux vector v is bounded by:

$$v_L \leq v \leq v_U$$

where v_L and v_U are vectors specifying the lower and upper bounds for each component of v . This approach ensures that the flux vectors v lie within a feasible region defined by the intersection of the null space of S and the convex polytope defined by the bounds. Type 1 constraint were integrated by constraining exchange fluxes. More in depth, for each medium metabolite, an exchange flux was included in the model having upper-bound set to zero and lower bound proportionally tuned to the uptaken metabolite concentration. RAS constraints were integrated by assuming that a reaction having lower RAS has lower capability to run its flux in within the network. For this reason, INTEGRATE makes the boundaries v_L and v_U of a given cell c dependent on the $\overline{\text{RAS}}_{c,r}$. The complete INTEGRATE procedure to limit the flux of an internal reaction r was modified as follows (type 2 constraints were not available):

1. FVA was performed to compute the effective minimum and maximum bounds of r across all the cell-lines. FVA was run over the generic ENGRO2 model, constrained by type 1 constraints only which are shared by all the bulk samples.
2. Once the vectors $v_{MIN,r}^c$ and $v_{MAX,r}^c$ were obtained by FVA, each cell-line model was differentiated by integrating RAS-dependent constraints: The reaction r in cell c can be mathematically described using the following constraints:

$$\overline{\text{RAS}}_{c,r} \cdot v_{MIN,r}^c \leq v_r^c \leq \overline{\text{RAS}}_{c,r} \cdot v_{MAX,r}^c \quad (2.5)$$

3. Otherwise, if r is not associated with a GPR:

$$v_{MIN,r}^c \leq v_r^c \leq v_{MAX,r}^c \quad (2.6)$$

Figure 2.3: An example of two cell-specific constraint-based polytopes generated from the same generic metabolic model by INTEGRATE. For example, given that the flux v_2 is up-regulated in model A and down-regulated in model B , the upper bound of flux v_2 is reduced in model B . The two obtained subregions can be internally sampled.

Computationally-derived fluxomics

All the different cell-specific models were sampled using the CBS and CHRR algorithms to obtain the predicted fluxes. The CBS algorithm generated 10,000 samples per cell, sharing the same random coefficients among the sampled models to avoid any bias related to coefficient randomness. Best practices for internal sampling of the polytopes were applied to effectively gather a representative set of fluxes using the CHRR algorithm. Specifically, 10 different batches of 1,000 samples each were run, with thinning set to 100. For each cell, a total of 10,000 samples were collected.

Given the high dimensionality of the sampled solutions (462 reactions) and the large number of sampled fluxes necessary to avoid false discoveries or weak distributions, various statistics were computed to capture the main characteristics of the sampled space: mean, median, mode and fluxes, and Spearman correlation with respect to the Biomass reaction. INTEGRATE, unlike scFEA, has the capacity to create cell-specific models that can be processed using various techniques such as FBA, FVA, pFBA and sensitivity analysis. In this thesis, all these techniques were utilized. Specifically, FBA, pFBA and sensitivity analysis were performed by selecting the Biomass reaction as the objective function.

2.3.2 scFEA

Single-cell flux estimation analysis (scFEA) is a novel computational method intended to estimate the relative rate of metabolic flux at single-cell resolution from single cell RNA-seq data [7]. Steady-state constraints, used by frameworks as INTEGRATE, may not be appropriate for diseases with significant metabolite imbalances, such as cancer. Moreover, constraint-based steady-state integration methods do not directly use gene expression to model cellular fluxes, but they are imposed as new constraints on the model to guide the search for solutions.

The generation of the scFEA fluxes has to be addressed to a collaboration with Dot. Fabio Marini (f.marini14@campus.unimib.it).

scFEA distinguishes itself from all these methods in the following ways:

- Linearity between gene expression and reaction rates is not assumed.
- Gene expression data is directly used to model cell fluxes without the need for an intermediary constraint-based model, which typically requires optimization techniques like FBA or flux sampling.
- It is not limited to relatively small portions of metabolic maps, such as INTEGRATE with ENGRO2, but can leverage complete metabolic maps.

In this thesis, scFEA was performed and validated over bulk samples data, thus bulk RNA-seq data, as done with the INTEGRATE pipeline. It is relevant to notice that INTEGRATE generates cell-specific metabolic models that can be successively sampled and analyzed, while scFEA generates a compact flux distribution for each input cell.

This method effectively addresses four computational challenges:

1. The metabolic conditions of cells are influenced by several fundamental factors. Chief among these is the availability of external nutrients, which plays a crucial role. This availability can vary widely and result in significant differences in cell phenotypes and metabolic states.
2. The entire human metabolic network is highly complex. Therefore, an appropriate reduction and reconstruction of the network are necessary to balance the characterization of the metabolic state with computational feasibility.
3. The intricate nonlinear relationship between transcriptomic expressions and metabolic reaction rates requires a more sophisticated model to fully leverage these connections.
4. Alternative enzymes with similar functions can lead to common metabolic phenotypes. However, which enzymes specifically share this common effect on altering metabolic flux remains largely unknown.

scFEA implements the following solutions, shown by Figure 2.4:

1. An optimization function derived from a probabilistic model to consider the budget constraints of the flow among numerous cells with different metabolic fluxes.
2. An approach to metabolic map reduction based on network topology and gene expression state.
3. A multilayer neural network model to capture the nonlinear dependency of metabolic flux on the expression of enzymatic genes.
4. A new graph neural network architecture and a solution to maximize the overall flow of intermediate substrates in all cells.

scFEA is based on Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) metabolic map [44] which was enriched and optimized and finally to have including 862 genes of 390 enzymes, 1880 reactions and 1219 metabolites. The elements of the metabolic map can be depicted as a factor graph, which is a structure that aids in analyzing the relationships between variables. In this context, a factor graph is a bipartite graph where nodes represent variables and factors. The variables correspond to reactions, while the factors are metabolites. These elements are linked together based on the stoichiometric matrix, a representation that outlines the reactions within a cell, detailing the amounts of each metabolite consumed or produced in a reaction. In the factor graph, an edge connects a reaction to a metabolite if that metabolite is either a substrate or a product of the reaction. Consequently, metabolites act as connecting nodes between different reactions, forming a network of interactions that illustrates the flow and clarifies the relationships between reactions and metabolites.

The complexity of the factor graph was reduced by leveraging its topological structure, grouping connected reactions into modules, also known as metabolic modules. This was done by ensuring that no intermediate metabolites had more than one incoming or outgoing reaction corresponding to multiple modules and that no intermediate metabolites had input or output fluxes different from the combined reactions or the module's inputs and outputs. Under these conditions and the flow balance condition, it was shown that changes in reactions within the module do not affect external reactions. Thus, solving the flow of each individual reaction within a unified module is equivalent to solving the module's flow. The combined reactions form a variable node containing multiple reactions in the factor graph. Specific classes were identified for metabolites, such as different types of fatty acids, pyrimidines, purines, and steroid hormones, forming highly connected metabolic pathways. Instead of solving the flow for each individual metabolite, metabolites of the same class were treated as a single factor. A truncated Gaussian model was used to determine which genes were

significantly expressed, removing those with expression values at or near zero to avoid skewing the network. Additionally, if any modules were disconnected from others after this removal, they were also eliminated. Finally, the modules were manually labeled into 22 supermodule classes based on their metabolic functions, such as purine synthesis, transporters and glycolysis.

From the perspective of the prediction model, the metabolic network, viewed as a factor graph, consists of modules represented as variables, metabolites represented as factors carrying a loss function to evaluate the flow imbalance between modules, and directed edges indicating whether a metabolite is used as an input or output of a metabolic module based on the stoichiometric matrix. The method uses two types of neural networks: one is a multilayer fully connected network used to model the nonlinear dependency of the flow $Flux_{m,j}$ between gene expression and reaction rates for the module, where $m = 1, \dots, M$ represents one of the possible M modules, and $j = 1, \dots, N$ represents one of the possible N cells sampled from single-cell RNA sequencing. The second type of neural network used is a graph neural network (GNN), which is particularly effective for improving flow estimates based on the network’s topology through the technique of belief propagation.

For each module m , associated genes $G^m = \{G_1^m, \dots, G_{i_m}^m\}$ with i_m being the number of genes in the module’s reactions are used. The network models the flow $Flux_{m,j}$ by taking gene expression values from sample j , denoted $G_j^m = \{G_{i_1,1}^m, \dots, G_{i_m,j}^m\}$, to find unknown reaction parameters θ_m . To avoid the trivial solution $Flux_{m,j} \equiv 0$, two constraints are introduced: the predicted flow $Flux_{m,j}$ must be non-negative, and within a supermodule, the total predicted flow must correlate with gene expression changes. Each module is represented by a neural network with three hidden layers, each containing eight nodes with the activation function $Tanhshrink(x) = x - tanh(x)$. Since the number of genes (input nodes) varies for each module, a dynamic method is used to create input nodes, setting the values of nodes corresponding to non-existing genes to zero, and no bias parameter is added for the input layer.

The networks aim to minimize the following loss function:

$$\begin{aligned}
L = & \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^K \left(\sum_{m \in F_{in}^{C_k}} Flux_{m,j} - \sum_{m' \in F_{out}^{C_k}} Flux_{m',j} \right)^2 \\
& + \alpha \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^M (|Flux_{m,j} - Flux_{m,j}|) \\
& + \beta \sum_{j=1}^N [1 - |cor(Flux_{:,j}^{SM}, GE_{:,j}^{SM})|] \\
& + \gamma \sum_{j=1}^N \left(\sum_{m=1}^M |Flux_{m,j}| - TA_j \right)^2.
\end{aligned} \tag{2.7}$$

Here, $F_{in}^{C_k}$ and $F_{out}^{C_k}$ represent the sets of reactions producing and consuming the component C_k based on the stoichiometric matrix; α , β , and γ are hyperparameters; cor denotes the Pearson correlation coefficient used to measure the consistency between gene expression and predicted flow; $Flux^{SM}$ and GE^{SM} are $NSM \times N$ matrices with NSM being the number of supermodules; $Flux_{m,j}^{SM}$ represents the sum of gene expressions in supermodules m in cell j ; and TA_j is a surrogate for the total metabolic activity level of cell j , assigned as the total expression of metabolic genes in cell j . The first, second, third, and fourth terms of L correspond to the flow balance constraint, non-negative flow, the consistency between predicted flow and total gene expression level of each supermodule, and the relative scale of the flow, respectively.

In the factor graph, variables are viewed as neural networks, and intermediate metabolites aggregate information between adjacent variables while ensuring balance between incoming and outgoing flows. The goal is to minimize a loss function without updating the flow in one module at a time, as intermediate substrates are influenced by multiple modules, making single updates computationally inefficient. Given the numerous flows, the information update strategy is not theoretically derivable. Therefore, backpropagation used in Markov random fields (Lan et al. 2006) is not applicable; instead, information transfer via belief propagation, typical of Graph Neural Networks (GNN), is used, leveraging the network topology to enhance predictions. L is minimized iteratively by reducing the flow imbalance of C_k and the weighted sum of the flow imbalance of C_k 's Hop-2 neighbors in the factor graph, i.e., those reachable within two edges from the intermediate node. The loss function minimized by the GNN is:

$$\begin{aligned}
L_k^* = & \sum_{j=1}^N \left(\sum_{m \in F_{in}^{C_k}} Flux_{m,j} - \sum_{m' \in F_{out}^{C_k}} Flux_{m',j} \right)^2 \\
& + \sum_{k'} W_{k'} \sum_{j=1}^N \left(\sum_{m \in F_{in}^{C_k}} Flux_{m,j} - \sum_{m' \in F_{out}^{C_k}} Flux_{m',j} \right)^2.
\end{aligned} \tag{2.8}$$

Here, $C_{k'}$ are the Hop-2 neighbors of C_k , and $W_{k'}$ is a value in $(0, 1]$ proportional to the total imbalance of all Hop-2 neighbors of $C_{k'}$ except C_k itself. The outputs produced by **scFEA** include θ_m for each module and the predicted metabolic flow for each cell $Flux_{m,j}$.

scFEA was experimentally validated using scRNA-seq data and matched metabolomics data under different biochemical conditions. The algorithm showed consistency between predicted fluxes and observed metabolite abundance variations. Validation steps included:

- Generating an scRNA-seq data set with matched metabolomics data on cells under perturbed oxygen and genetic conditions.
- Applying scFEA to this data set and comparing predicted fluxes with observed metabolite variations.

A Network reduction and reconstruction into factor graph

B Flux Estimation

$$L = \sum_{\text{Cells}} \sum_{\text{Metabolize}} \text{Flux Balance Loss} + \sum_{\text{Modules}} \text{Non-Negative Loss} + \sum_{\text{Modules}} \text{Inconsistency with Gene Expression} + \text{Flux Scale}$$

Figure 2.4: The computational framework of scFEA: (A) Metabolic Reduction and Reconstruction: A metabolic map is reduced and reconstructed into a factor graph based on network topology, significantly non-zero gene expressions, and user inputs. (B) Prediction of the Cell-Wise Fluxome Using a Novel Graph Neural Network Architecture: A loss function (L) composed of terms for flux balance, non-negative flux, coherence between predicted flux and gene expression, and flux scale constraint, is used to estimate cell-wise metabolic flux from scRNA-seq data. Detailed models and formulations are provided in the Results and Methods sections. Image taken from [7].

2.4 Preprocessing

2.4.1 Transcriptomics denoising: MAGIC

Single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-seq) is gaining traction in biomedical research. However, a major challenge is that only a small portion (typically between 5% and 15%) of each cell’s transcriptome is captured [45]. This limitation in detection, particularly for genes with low expression levels, can lead to a phenomenon known as ”dropout” where expressed genes fail to be detected. This problem affects the signal for every gene, resulting in the loss of gene-gene interactions in the data and masking all but the most robust associations. To address these challenges, a computational method named MAGIC (Markov Affinity-based Graph Imputation of Cells) was developed to recover missing gene expression in single-cell data [8]. MAGIC leverages the large sample sizes in transcriptomics to disseminate information across similar cells through data diffusion. This technique imputes probable gene expression in each cell, thereby unveiling the underlying biological structure. MAGIC employs signal-processing principles akin to those used to enhance blurry and grainy images. The developers rigorously validated MAGIC across various biological systems and found it effective in restoring gene-gene relationships and revealing additional biological structures. Initially conceived as a denoising algorithm for single-cell transcriptomics data, MAGIC was applied and validated for bulk samples, demonstrating its efficacy.

MAGIC processes an observed count matrix to generate an imputed count matrix that likely represents gene expression levels for each individual cell. This imputation is accomplished by utilizing data diffusion among similar cells. For any given cell, MAGIC first identifies the most similar cells and aggregates their gene expression data to impute values for the target cell, thereby correcting for dropouts and other noise sources. However, due to the inherent sparsity of the data, the nearest neighbors identified in the raw data may not accurately represent the most biologically similar cells. To address this issue, data diffusion is employed to construct a weighted affinity matrix that more accurately reflects the neighborhood of similar cells. This matrix is then used to restore the data. With a sufficient number of cells, this methodology increases the weights on cells that exhibit similarity across a broad range of biological processes.

MAGIC algorithm starts with a count matrix $D_{n \cdot m}$ representing n cells and m genes and return as output a new matrix $D_{imputed}$. Each cell phenotype is described a vector in the m -dimensional space, while the counts in $D_{imputed}$ represents the likely expression vectors obtained through the data diffusion process. The key of the algorithm is the effective construction of a neighbourhood of similar cells based on a specific similarity metric. The intrinsic data sparsity of count matrices lead to the need of a more complex computation than a simple k-nearest neighbors graph to link similar cells.

The MAGIC algorithm can be summarized in five main steps (see Algorithm 1 for the pseudocode):

1. Data processing of D through PCA to reduce the dimensionality of the matrix.
2. Converting cell distances to affinities using an adaptive Gaussian Kernel, so that similarity between two cells decreases exponentially with their distance.
3. The affinity matrix A , computed in the previous step, is converted into a Markov transition matrix M , representing the probability distribution of transitioning from each cell to every other cell in the data in a single step.
4. Data diffusion through exponentiation of M , to filter out similarity based on high frequencies that typically represent noise and increase the similarity based on strong trends in the data.
5. Once the affinity matrix is constructed, the imputation step of MAGIC involves sharing information between cells in the resulting neighborhoods through matrix multiplication

$$D_{imputed} = M^t \cdot D \quad (2.9)$$

Algorithm 1 MAGIC

- 1: **procedure** MAGIC(D , t)
 - 2: $D \leftarrow$ preprocessed(D)
 - 3: $Dist \leftarrow$ compute distance matrix(D)
 - 4: $A \leftarrow$ compute affinity matrix($Dist$)
 - 5: $M \leftarrow$ compute markov affinity matrix(A)
 - 6: $D_{imputed} \leftarrow M^t \cdot D$
 - 7: $D_{rescaled} \leftarrow$ Rescale($D_{imputed}$)
 - 8: $D_{imputed} \leftarrow D_{rescaled}$
 - 9: **end procedure**
-

The entire scRNA-seq matrix can be represented as a nearest neighbors graph where each node represents a cell and edges connect most similar cells, based upon gene expression. The procedure can be described as follows:

1. Data preparation

- To stabilise variance and handle large range differences in expression levels, the application of a log transformation to the count matrix is suggested.

- Compute D_{pca} to retain only a predefined number of principal components (*PCs*). This reduced matrix is used to compute the affinity matrix, while the imputation step works the full data matrix.

2. Distance matrix

- Compute the cell-cell distance matrix $Dist$ between cells over D_{pca} . The Euclidean distance between two cells $p = (p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n)$ and $q = (q_1, q_2, \dots, q_n)$ in an n -dimensional space is given by:

$$d(p, q) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (p_i - q_i)^2} \quad (2.10)$$

3. Affinity matrix

- Define the affinity matrix A using the Gaussian kernel on the distance matrix $Dist$:

$$A_{ij} = \exp\left(-\frac{\|x_i - x_j\|^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (2.11)$$

where x_i and x_j are the expression profiles of cells i and j , and σ is a scaling parameter. The Gaussian kernel is used to convert distances into affinities in such a way that similarity between cells decreases exponentially with their initial distances. A fixed kernel would alter and deform the shape of the data as cells in denser regions have more neighbors, while cells in sparse areas have fewer cells to exchange information. The same data with the adaptive kernel as in MAGIC reveals finer structures in the data. Instead of fixing a single value for the kernel width σ , this value is adapted for each cell, based on its local density. In this way, the kernel is wider in sparse areas and smaller in dense areas. Specifically:

$$\sigma_i = distance(i, neighbor(i, ka)) \quad (2.12)$$

where σ_i is the kernel standard deviation for cell i and $neighbor(i, ka)$ represents the distance of cell i from its ka -neighbor. Each cell is allowed to have at most k neighbors where $k = 3ka$.

4. Markov Transition Matrix

- Normalize the affinity matrix A to obtain the Markov transition matrix M , where M_{ij} represents the probability to transit from cell i to j in one step:

$$M_{ij} = \frac{A_{ij}}{\sum_k A_{ik}} \quad (2.13)$$

5. Diffusion Process

- Apply the diffusion operator to propagate information across the graph. This is achieved by raising the Markov transition matrix to a power t , where t is the diffusion time parameter. Raising M to the power t results in a matrix where each entry represents the probability that a random walk of length t starting at cell i will reach cell j . Thus, when a Markov matrix is raised to a power, it reduces the importance of noise dimensions with near-zero explanatory power. In this process, the signal is filtered from the noise. Therefore, as t increases, similarity based on high-frequency trends (which often correspond to technological noise) decreases, and the affinity matrix represents similarity along lower-frequency trends that follow data density. As a result, after raising M to a power, phenotypically similar cells should have a strong weighted entry, while spurious neighbors are down-weighted.
- The true manifold structure of the data is represented by the top eigenvectors of M , while the remaining eigenvectors are likely indicative of noise. The eigenvalues, which fall within the range $[1,0]$, are gradually diminished through exponentiation.
- The potential diffusion times belong to two regimes: an imputation regime and a smoothing regime. The initial steps of diffusion, referred to as the imputation regime, reduce the noise dimensions, bringing these small eigenvalues to zero and eliminating most of the noise in the data. As t increases, cells learn missing values from their neighbors, and it captures the correct relationships between cells that are biologically very similar but were only separated by collection artifacts. Thus, in the imputation regime, the imputed matrix changes rapidly from one iteration to the next.
- In the smoothing regime, t is sufficiently large to have reconstructed the manifold with the majority of the noise eliminated. When diffusion has created a shared support for cells, additional diffusion will smooth out the lower frequency trends in the data, which probably represent genuine biological signals. Thus, optimal tuning of t requires determining the point at which noise removal begins to turn into signal removal.
- MAGIC algorithm optimizes t by computing the R^2 coefficient between the M matrix at $t - 1$ and t . If the change in R^2 is less than 0.05 (the change in correlation between the two matrices is less than 5%), then $t - 1$ has to be used:

$$R^2(M^t, M^{t-1}) = \frac{1 - \text{SSE}(M^t, M^{t-1})}{1 - \text{SST}(M^t, M^{t-1})} \quad (2.14)$$

where SSE is the sum of squared error and SST is the sum of squared total.

6. Imputation

- Impute the gene expression values by diffusing the original log-scaled expression matrix D using the diffusion operator:

$$D_{imputed} = M^t * D \quad (2.15)$$

where $D_{imputed}$ is the imputed gene expression matrix. In the imputation step, MAGIC enhances the data by leveraging information from cells within each neighborhood. This is achieved by multiplying the transition matrix with the original data matrix, effectively aligning cells with their underlying manifold. During this data diffusion process, cells exchange information with their local neighbors, analogous to the diffusion of heat through data. Raising the diffusion operator to the t -th power corresponds to a t -step random walk through the data. This exponentiation acts as a low-pass filter on the eigenvalues, removing noise dimensions with small eigenvalues while learning the manifold structure. Although PCA is used to enhance robustness when computing the affinity matrix, the imputation is performed on the count matrix before applying PCA. As a result, while data is averaged across cells, each individual cell retains a unique neighborhood, leading to a distinct expression vector for each cell.

MAGIC modifies the data by imputing missing values and smoothing the expression of genes across similar cells. Specifically, it:

- **Denoising:** Reduces the technical noise by averaging the expression values over similar cells, thereby enhancing the signal-to-noise ratio.
- **Imputation:** Fills in the dropout events, which are common in single-cell RNA-seq data, where a gene may appear to be unexpressed in a cell due to technical limitations rather than biological absence.
- **Smoothing:** Ensures that the gene expression levels are more consistent among similar cells, thereby recovering continuous gene expression patterns that may be disrupted by technical noise.
- **Preservation of Biological Variability:** Maintains the underlying biological variability while reducing the random noise, allowing for more accurate downstream analyses such as clustering, trajectory inference, and differential expression.

It is relevant to discuss MAGIC robustness relating to its parameters and the capacity to avoid introducing numerical artifacts that could bias the biological clusters. MAGIC requires three inputs: ka (to set the adaptive kernel to the distance of the k -th nearest neighbor), t (the number of times the matrix M is powered), and $npca$ (the number of PCA components used to construct the affinity matrix). MAGIC was tested by [8] to identify optimal parameter ranges to avoid over-smoothing of the dataset. In particular:

- MAGIC is robust with $ka \leq 30$, while higher values could lead to over-smoothing. MAGIC sets the maximum number of K-nearest neighbors to $3 \cdot ka$.
- MAGIC is robust with $t \leq 24$, while higher values could also lead to over-smoothing.
- MAGIC is highly robust with respect to the number of PCs used. Generally, using too few PCs may fail to capture sufficient variance of the dataset.

While MAGIC recovers structure by diffusing values between neighboring cells, it is crucial that values do not transfer between different clusters. In fact, [8] demonstrated that the cluster structure remains intact even after applying MAGIC.

It is important to highlight that MAGIC was originally intended for single-cell denoising, which is characterized by a very high level of noise. This is due to the fact that scRNA sequencing technologies suffer from many sources of technical noise, including dropout, which can obscure important gene-gene relationships [8]. In contrast, this analysis focused on bulk RNA-seq data, where the RNA-seq data derives from multiple cells of the same tissue, thus reducing the technical difficulties seen in single-cell sequencing. As previously mentioned, too high values of ka and t could lead to over-smoothing and thus compromise the original cluster structure. To avoid over-smoothing, a conservative approach to the algorithm’s parameters was adopted, as shown in Table 2.1. These parameter values are recommended by [46] and are at the lower end of the ranges suggested by the original MAGIC study.

Table 2.1: MAGIC parameters

Parameter	Symbol	Value
K-nn for σ_i	ka	5
Maximum K-nn	k	$3 \cdot 5 = 15$
Diffusion operator power	t	3
Principal components	PCs	100

2.4.2 Scaling

In preprocessing data for machine learning models, it is often essential to scale the features to ensure they are on a similar scale. Two common scaling techniques provided by [22] are Min-Max Scaling and Standard Scaling. Each omic dataset was pre-processed using both methods before applying PCA, and subsequently, clustering, to ensure comprehensive coverage.

Min-Max Scaling

Min-Max Scaling, also known as normalization, scales the data to a fixed range, typically $[0, 1]$. This scaling method transforms each feature individually such that it is bounded by a specified minimum and maximum value. The formula for Min-Max Scaling is:

$$X' = \frac{X - X_{\min}}{X_{\max} - X_{\min}} \quad (2.16)$$

where X is the original feature vector, X_{\min} and X_{\max} are the minimum and maximum values of the feature, respectively, and X' is the scaled feature. This transformation ensures that all features are in the same range, which can be particularly useful for algorithms that rely on distance calculations such as k-means clustering and k-nearest neighbors. It is useful when the data does not have outliers and when the features have a bounded range. It is often preferred for algorithms that do not assume normally distributed data.

Standard Scaler

Standard Scaling, also known as z-score normalization, transforms the data to have a mean of zero and a standard deviation of one. This method standardizes each feature individually by removing the mean and scaling to unit variance. The formula for Standard Scaling is:

$$X' = \frac{X - \mu}{\sigma} \quad (2.17)$$

where X is the original feature vector, μ is the mean of the feature, σ is the standard deviation of the feature, and X' is the standardized feature. This transformation ensures that each feature contributes equally to the analysis, which can be particularly useful for algorithms that assume normally distributed data, such as linear regression and principal component analysis (PCA). It is useful when the data has outliers or when the features have different units or scales. It is often preferred for algorithms that assume normally distributed data.

2.4.3 Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a widely-used dimensionality reduction technique in machine learning and data analysis. It transforms the data into a new coordinate system such that the greatest variances by any projection of the data come to lie on the first principal component, the second greatest variances on the second principal component, and so on. This technique is particularly useful for reducing the dimensionality of large datasets, improving computational efficiency, and removing noise.

The cumulative explained variance represents the percentage of the original total variance captured by the first n principal components. Each omic dataset was subjected to dimensionality reduction to facilitate clustering analysis. For each omic dataset, n different components were selected such that their cumulative explained variance was at least 80% (see Table A.1 in appendix). The transcriptomics dataset, given their extremely high dimensionality, did not reach this threshold and 70 principal components were chosen based on the elbow method. The formula for cumulative explained variance is:

$$\text{Cumulative Explained Variance} = \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\lambda_i}{\sum_{j=1}^p \lambda_j} \right) \times 100\% \quad (2.18)$$

where λ_i is the eigenvalue of the i -th principal component, and p is the total number of original variables.

The goal of PCA is to identify the principal components that capture the maximum variance in the data. The steps involved in PCA are as follows:

1. Standardize the Data:

- Given a data matrix $\mathbf{X} \in R^{n \times p}$, where n is the number of samples and p is the number of features, standardize the data to have a mean of zero and a standard deviation of one:

$$\mathbf{X}_{\text{std}} = \frac{\mathbf{X} - \mu}{\sigma} \quad (2.19)$$

where μ is the mean and σ is the standard deviation of each feature.

2. Compute the Covariance Matrix:

- Calculate the covariance matrix \mathbf{C} of the standardized data:

$$\mathbf{C} = \frac{1}{n-1} \mathbf{X}_{\text{std}}^\top \mathbf{X}_{\text{std}} \quad (2.20)$$

3. Eigenvalue Decomposition:

- Perform eigenvalue decomposition on the covariance matrix to obtain the eigenvalues and eigenvectors:

$$\mathbf{C}\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{V}\mathbf{\Lambda} \quad (2.21)$$

where \mathbf{V} is the matrix of eigenvectors and $\mathbf{\Lambda}$ is the diagonal matrix of eigenvalues.

4. Select Principal Components:

- Sort the eigenvalues in descending order and select the top k eigenvectors corresponding to the largest eigenvalues. These eigenvectors form the principal components.

5. Transform the Data:

- Project the original standardized data onto the selected principal components to obtain the reduced-dimensionality data:

$$\mathbf{X}_{\text{PCA}} = \mathbf{X}_{\text{std}}\mathbf{V}_k \quad (2.22)$$

where \mathbf{V}_k contains the top k eigenvectors.

PCA offers several benefits and applications, including:

When using PCA, it is important to consider the following points:

- **Linear Assumption:** PCA assumes that the principal components are linear combinations of the original features. It may not capture complex, non-linear relationships in the data.
- **Variance Retention:** The number of principal components to retain is a critical decision. It is often based on the proportion of variance that needs to be preserved, which can be determined using a scree plot or by setting a cumulative explained variance threshold.
- **Interpretability:** The principal components are linear combinations of the original features and may not always be easily interpretable in the context of the original features.

2.5 Clustering Analysis

The aim of this thesis is to characterize the metabolic heterogeneity of cancer cells by utilizing various biological data, such as RNA-seq and fluxomics, referring to the same set of cells. To achieve this, clustering analysis was employed to uncover hidden associations and patterns within each of the analyzed omics datasets. Subsequently, the subpopulations identified in each omic were compared.

Each data source underwent a clustering grid search for hyperparameter optimization based solely on internal evaluation metrics, such as Silhouette and Davies-Bouldin scores. Following this, biomarkers were identified, along with a graphical association analysis between clusters and cell metadata, including cancer histology, pathology, and primary site. Biomarkers were not extensively interpreted, as it is beyond the original scope and would require expertise from life scientists.

2.5.1 Hyperparameters tuning

The hyperparameters optimization was not guided by external evaluation metrics, such as v-measure, to maximize the concordance with a ground truth, but was performed independently. In order to run an exhaustive unsupervised analysis, four main clustering algorithm families were tested:

- **Centroid-based** clustering algorithms, such as K-means [20] and K-medoids [21], are most effective when data is likely to form spherical clusters of similar sizes. These algorithms work well with large datasets and are efficient in terms of computational complexity. K-means is particularly useful when the goal is to minimize variance within clusters, while K-medoids is more robust to noise and outliers.
- **Hierarchical** clustering algorithms, like agglomerative clustering [22], are ideal when the data has a hierarchical structure. These algorithms do not require the number of clusters to be specified in advance and are beneficial when the dataset contains nested clusters. They are also useful for smaller datasets or when the computational cost is not a primary concern.
- **Density-based** clustering algorithms, such as HDBSCAN [47], are suitable for identifying clusters of arbitrary shapes and handling datasets with noise. They are particularly effective when the clusters are densely packed and separated by low-density regions. HDBSCAN is beneficial when dealing with spatial data or datasets where clusters are expected to have varying sizes and shapes.
- **Graph-based** clustering algorithms, like the Leiden algorithm [23], are optimal for large-scale networks or graph-structured data. These

algorithms are designed to optimize modularity or other community detection measures and are effective in uncovering complex relationships and communities within the data. The Leiden algorithm, in particular, is well-suited for large datasets as it improves the quality and speed of clustering compared to similar algorithms like Louvain [48].

All the algorithm implementations are sourced from scikit-learn [22], except for the Leiden algorithm, which is implemented by the scanpy library [46].

Clustering hyperparameter optimization is crucial as it significantly enhances the performance of clustering algorithms. By fine-tuning hyperparameters, one can achieve more meaningful and well-separated clusters, leading to better data segmentation and more reliable insights. This process helps minimize errors, improve computational efficiency, and ensure that the clustering model generalizes well to unseen data. To this end, an extensive hyperparameter grid search was conducted to obtain a well-informed set of clustering settings for each pair of omic dataset and clustering algorithm. The tested parameters and values are reported in Table 2.2.

Table 2.2: Clustering hyperparameters grid-search.

K-means / K-medoids	
Hyperparameter	Values
K	From 2 to 11
Agglomerative	
Hyperparameter	Values
K	From 2 to 11
Distance metric	Euclidean, Cosine, Manhattan
HDBSCAN	
Hyperparameter	Values
Minimum cluster size	5, 10, 15, 25, 30
Distance metric	Euclidean, Manhattan
Leiden	
Hyperparameter	Values
Neighbors	15, 30, 50
Distance metric	Euclidean, Cosine, Manhattan
Resolution	0.1, 0.2, 0.5, 1, 2, 4

K-means

K-means is a popular clustering algorithm used to partition a dataset into K distinct, non-overlapping subsets. The algorithm operates as follows:

1. Initialize K centroids $\mu_1, \mu_2, \dots, \mu_K$ randomly selected from the data points.
2. Assign each data point x_i to the nearest centroid C_j based on the Euclidean distance:

$$C_j = \{x_i : \|x_i - \mu_j\|^2 \leq \|x_i - \mu_l\|^2 \quad \forall l, 1 \leq l \leq K\} \quad (2.23)$$

3. Update the centroid of each cluster to be the mean of the data points assigned to it:

$$\mu_j = \frac{1}{|C_j|} \sum_{x_i \in C_j} x_i \quad (2.24)$$

4. Repeat steps 2 and 3 until the centroids converge (i.e., the assignments no longer change) or a maximum number of iterations is reached.

The Mini-Batch K-means variant was used to handle the most computationally intensive clustering tasks due to the large number of data points being clustered. This approach was particularly applied to the sampled fluxes, which were processed in batches of 1024 points. Mini-Batch K-means is an efficient version of the standard K-means algorithm. It uses small, random subsets of the dataset (mini-batches) to update the cluster centers, rather than using the entire dataset. This reduces the computational load and speeds up the convergence, making it suitable for large datasets.

K-medoids

K-medoids is a clustering algorithm similar to K-means, but instead of using the mean of the data points as the cluster center, it uses an actual data point (medoid) that minimizes the sum of dissimilarities within a cluster. The algorithm proceeds as follows:

1. Initialize K medoids m_1, m_2, \dots, m_K randomly selected from the data points.
2. Assign each data point x_i to the nearest medoid C_j based on a specified distance metric $d(x_i, m_j)$:

$$C_j = \{x_i : d(x_i, m_j) \leq d(x_i, m_l) \quad \forall l, 1 \leq l \leq K\} \quad (2.25)$$

3. For each medoid, compute the total cost of swapping the medoid with each point in the cluster and choose the point that minimizes the total cost:

$$\text{Cost}(m_j) = \sum_{x_i \in C_j} d(x_i, m_j) \quad (2.26)$$

4. Repeat steps 2 and 3 until the medoids stabilize or a maximum number of iterations is reached.

Agglomerative

Agglomerative clustering is a hierarchical clustering technique that builds nested clusters by repeatedly merging pairs of clusters. The process is as follows:

1. Start with each data point as a separate cluster.
2. Compute the distance between all pairs of clusters. Let $D(A, B)$ represent the distance between clusters A and B .
3. Merge the pair of clusters with the smallest distance:

$$(A, B) = \arg \min_{A, B} D(A, B) \quad (2.27)$$

4. Update the distance matrix to reflect the distance between the newly formed cluster $A \cup B$ and the remaining clusters.
5. Repeat steps 2-4 until all data points are merged into a single cluster or a desired number of clusters is achieved.

Different linkage criteria (e.g., single, complete, average) can be used to determine the distance between clusters.

HDBSCAN

HDBSCAN (Hierarchical Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise) is an extension of DBSCAN that finds clusters of varying densities. The algorithm works as follows:

1. Transform the space according to the density of data points using a mutual reachability distance:

$$d_{\text{mreach}}(x_i, x_j) = \max(\text{core}_k(x_i), \text{core}_k(x_j), d(x_i, x_j)) \quad (2.28)$$

where $\text{core}_k(x)$ is the core distance of point x .

2. Construct a minimum spanning tree (MST) of the distance-weighted graph.
3. Condense the MST by repeatedly removing the longest edges, forming a hierarchy of connected components.
4. Extract the clusters from the condensed tree using a stability-based criterion to select the most persistent clusters.

Leiden

The Leiden algorithm is a community detection method used primarily for detecting communities in large networks. It improves upon the Louvain algorithm by ensuring better-quality partitions. The process is as follows:

1. Initialize each node i as its own community C_i .
2. Move nodes to neighboring communities to optimize the local modularity:

$$\Delta Q = \sum_i \left[\frac{k_i^{\text{intra}}}{2m} - \left(\frac{k_i}{2m} \right)^2 \right] \quad (2.29)$$

where k_i^{intra} is the sum of the weights of the edges within the community containing i , k_i is the sum of the weights of all edges attached to node i , and m is the sum of the weights of all edges in the network.

3. Refine the partitions by identifying and merging sub-communities within each community.
4. Aggregate the network based on the refined partitions and repeat the process until the partitions no longer change.

2.5.2 Clusterings comparison

Following the single-omic clustering analysis, it was needed to numerically evaluate the concordance level in capturing biological heterogeneity among different omics datasets. This evaluation was conducted using external metrics such as Normalized Mutual Information (NMI), Homogeneity, and Completeness. Such analysis allowed to evaluate the integration quality of INTEGRATE and scFEA by avoiding the benchmarking problem. At first glance, it might seem logical to select the set of hyperparameters that yield the highest concordance level for each pair of omics. However, this approach was dismissed due to two main limitations. Firstly, maximizing external evaluation metrics between omics would require using many clustering versions of the same omic for each pair, making it impossible to identify a unique

and most representative solution. For example, RNA-seq preprocessed with a standard scaler and clustered with K-means ($K=3$) could be optimal for maximizing NMI with predicted fluxes by scFEA. Simultaneously, RNA-seq preprocessed with a min-max scaler and clustered with K-means ($K=9$) might be preferred when compared with fluxes predicted by CBS. Secondly, only two omics datasets, metabolomics and RNA-seq, are derived from laboratory experiments. All predicted fluxes and derived omics originate from two computational frameworks (INTEGRATE and scFEA), which are strictly dependent on cell transcriptomics, and their robustness or capacity to capture metabolic heterogeneity is not guaranteed.

The only omic that is entirely independent of other data sources and closest to the actual metabolic profile of the analyzed cancer cells is intracellular metabolomics. Even if a specific enzyme is overexpressed in a cell (given by transcriptomics), the absence of the associated metabolite will reduce the overall reaction fluxes. Therefore, intracellular metabolomics was selected as the benchmark. Generally, metabolism depends on both transcriptomics and metabolite substrates. However, metabolomics is better suited as a benchmark for evaluating clusterings concordance levels because it is not directly connected to any other omic under analysis. Specifically, RNA-seq is used by INTEGRATE to compute RAS, create cell-specific models, sample the feasible regions, and compute all the derived statistics, and by scFEA to directly predict flux distributions.

In more detail, for a given omic, all clustering settings were evaluated in terms of various external evaluation metrics, such as Normalized Mutual Information (NMI), with respect to the benchmark set of labels derived from the best metabolomics clustering, as determined by internal metrics. In other words, a single clustering setting was chosen for each omic to optimize the concordance level with metabolomics.

2.5.3 Internal Evaluation Metrics

Internal evaluation metrics assess the quality of clustering based on the data itself without reference to external labels. These metrics help to evaluate how well the clusters are separated and how compact the clusters are. Below, four commonly used internal evaluation metrics are described: Silhouette Score [49], Calinski-Harabasz Index [50], Davies-Bouldin Index [51], and Density-Based Clustering Validation (DBCV) [24].

Silhouette Score

The Silhouette Score measures how similar an object is to its own cluster compared to other clusters. It is defined for each sample and can be averaged to provide an overall score.

$$s(i) = \frac{b(i) - a(i)}{\max(a(i), b(i))} \quad (2.30)$$

where $a(i)$ is the average distance from the i -th sample to all other points in the same cluster, and $b(i)$ is the minimum average distance from the i -th sample to all points in the nearest cluster to which i does not belong. The Silhouette Score ranges from -1 to 1, where a high value indicates that the sample is well matched to its own cluster and poorly matched to neighboring clusters.

Pros:

- Appropriate for evaluating clustering algorithms where the clusters are expected to be convex and well-separated.
- Useful when the number of clusters is known or can be varied to find the optimal clustering.

Cons:

- Not suitable for clusters with non-convex shapes or clusters with varying density.
- Sensitive to the definition of distance or similarity metrics.

Calinski-Harabasz Index

The Calinski-Harabasz Index, also known as the Variance Ratio Criterion, evaluates the ratio of the sum of between-cluster dispersion and within-cluster dispersion. It is defined as:

$$CH = \frac{\text{trace}(\mathbf{B}_k)}{\text{trace}(\mathbf{W}_k)} \times \frac{n - k}{k - 1} \quad (2.31)$$

where \mathbf{B}_k is the between-cluster dispersion matrix, \mathbf{W}_k is the within-cluster dispersion matrix, n is the number of samples, and k is the number of clusters. A higher Calinski-Harabasz score indicates better-defined clusters.

Pros:

- Effective for evaluating clustering when the clusters are expected to be spherical and equally sized.
- Suitable for algorithms like K-means which assume spherical clusters.

Cons:

- Assumes clusters are spherical and may not perform well with clusters of arbitrary shapes.
- Sensitive to the number of clusters, which needs to be specified beforehand.

Davies-Bouldin Index

The Davies-Bouldin Index evaluates the average similarity ratio of each cluster with its most similar cluster. It is defined as:

$$DB = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k \max_{j \neq i} \left(\frac{s_i + s_j}{d_{ij}} \right) \quad (2.32)$$

where s_i is the average distance between each point in cluster i and the centroid of cluster i , s_j is the average distance for cluster j , and d_{ij} is the distance between the centroids of clusters i and j . A lower Davies-Bouldin Index indicates better clustering.

Pros:

- Suitable for comparing different clustering algorithms or configurations to determine the best clustering structure.
- Effective when the clustering algorithms produce clusters of different shapes and sizes.

Cons:

- Sensitive to the number of clusters.
- The distance metric used can significantly affect the index value, requiring careful selection of the metric.

Density-Based Clustering Validation (DBCV)

The DBCV metric assesses the quality of a clustering result based on the density of points within clusters and the separation between clusters. It is defined as:

$$DBCV = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k \text{Score}(C_i)}{k} \quad (2.33)$$

where $\text{Score}(C_i)$ is a function that evaluates the density-connectedness within cluster i and the separation between cluster i and other clusters. A higher DBCV score indicates better clustering.

Pros:

- Ideal for evaluating clustering algorithms that form clusters of varying shapes and densities, such as DBSCAN.
- Useful in identifying meaningful clusters in datasets with noise and outliers.

Cons:

- Computationally intensive, especially for large datasets.
- The definition of the scoring function can vary, impacting the results.

2.5.4 External Evaluation Metrics

External evaluation metrics assess the quality of clustering by comparing the clustering results to external ground truth labels. These metrics help to evaluate the degree to which the clustering corresponds to the known class labels. Homogeneity, completeness, normalized mutual information score (NMI), and adjusted Rand index (ARI) were used to define a robust benchmarking pipeline.

Figure 2.5: a) Homogeneity = 1 and completeness < 1. b) Homogeneity = 0 and completeness = 1. c) Homogeneity < 1 and completeness = 1. d) Homogeneity = 1 and completeness = 0.

Homogeneity

Homogeneity measures whether each cluster contains only members of a single class. It is defined as:

$$h = 1 - \frac{H(C|K)}{H(C)} \quad (2.34)$$

where $H(C|K)$ is the conditional entropy of the class distribution given the cluster assignment, and $H(C)$ is the entropy of the class distribution. A homogeneity score of 1 indicates perfect homogeneity.

Completeness

Completeness measures whether all members of a given class are assigned to the same cluster. It is defined as:

$$c = 1 - \frac{H(K|C)}{H(K)} \quad (2.35)$$

where $H(K|C)$ is the conditional entropy of the cluster assignment given the class distribution, and $H(K)$ is the entropy of the cluster distribution. A completeness score of 1 indicates perfect completeness.

Normalized mutual information (NMI)

The NMI, also known as v-measure [52], is the harmonic mean of homogeneity and completeness. It is the normalized version of the Mutual Information (MI) used to scale the results between 0 (no mutual information) and 1 (perfect correlation). It is defined as:

$$NMI = 2 \times \frac{\text{homogeneity} \times \text{completeness}}{\text{homogeneity} + \text{completeness}} \quad (2.36)$$

This metric balances both the homogeneity and completeness (see Figure 2.5) scores to provide a single measure of the clustering quality. It is preferred over supervised learning evaluation metrics, such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F-measure because of the following properties:

- **Symmetry:** NMI treats homogeneity and completeness equally, ensuring that both the compactness of clusters (homogeneity) and the coverage of classes (completeness) are taken into account. This symmetry is advantageous because it provides a balanced evaluation of clustering performance.
- **Independence from Cluster Number:** Unlike accuracy or F-measure, NMI does not assume a fixed number of clusters, making it more suitable for scenarios where the number of clusters may vary or is not known a priori. This flexibility allows for more general applicability across different clustering tasks.
- **Penalization of Random Assignments:** NMI effectively penalizes random cluster assignments, ensuring that the metric reflects meaningful clustering structures rather than arbitrary groupings. This property

helps in distinguishing between genuine clustering performance and coincidental alignments with the ground truth.

- **Handling of Class Imbalances:** NMI is robust to class imbalances, which are common in real-world datasets. Traditional supervised metrics can be heavily influenced by dominant classes, whereas NMI provides a more equitable evaluation by considering the overall distribution of classes within clusters.

The Adjusted Mutual Information (AMI) is an adjustment of the MI and NMI scores to account for chance [53]. It accounts for the fact that the NMI, and MI, are generally higher for two clusterings with a larger number of clusters, regardless of whether there is actually more information shared. The NMI was preferred over homogeneity and completeness for its ability to represent both clustering properties.

Adjusted Rand index (ARI)

The Adjusted Rand Index (ARI) [54] is a measure of similarity between two data clustering that corrects for chance. It is an adjusted version of the Rand Index (RI), which considers all pairs of samples and counts pairs that are assigned in the same or different clusters in the predicted and true clustering. The adjustment accounts for the expected similarity of all pairwise comparisons between clustering randomly.

Given a set of n elements $S = \{O_1, O_2, \dots, O_n\}$ and two clusterings of these elements, $U = \{U_1, U_2, \dots, U_r\}$ and $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$, let a be the number of pairs of elements that are in the same set in both U and V , and b be the number of pairs of elements that are in different sets in both U and V . The Rand Index (RI) is defined as:

$$RI = \frac{a + b}{\binom{n}{2}} \quad (2.37)$$

where $\binom{n}{2}$ is the total number of pairs of elements.

The Adjusted Rand Index (ARI) adjusts this index to account for the expected similarity of all pairwise comparisons between clustering randomly. The ARI is defined as:

$$ARI = \frac{RI - E[RI]}{\max(RI) - E[RI]} \quad (2.38)$$

where $E[RI]$ is the expected Rand Index of random clusterings and $\max(RI)$ is the maximum Rand Index.

2.5.5 Biomarkers

Biological markers, or biomarkers, are critical indicators used in the identification and characterization of various biological states, including disease conditions. Biomarkers play a crucial role in interpreting the complex data derived from different omics analyses, facilitating the understanding of underlying biological processes.

One of the key motivations for identifying biomarkers is their interpretability. Biomarkers provide a tangible link between the vast and often abstract datasets generated through techniques such as RNA-seq and metabolomics, and the concrete biological phenomena they represent. This interpretability is essential for translating complex omics data into actionable insights that can drive further biological research and potential clinical applications. In this thesis, the identification of biomarkers was performed using the Wilcoxon rank-sum test. This non-parametric test is typically employed to compare the distributions of gene expression levels between different groups. More generally, it can be applied to other omics, such as metabolomics and fluxomics, to identify the metabolites with the highest concentrations or the reactions with the highest fluxes. The test statistic is given by:

$$W = \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} R(X_i) \quad (2.39)$$

where n_1 is the sample size of the first group, X_i is, for example, the expression value of the i -th gene in the first group and $R(X_i)$ is the rank of X_i in the combined sample of both groups. By employing the Wilcoxon rank-sum test, it is possible to identify genes, metabolites, or reactions that exhibit statistically significant differences between groups, thereby highlighting potential biomarkers within clusters. The dimensions of each cluster/group were scaled between 0 and 1 as done by the minmax scaler to facilitate the comparison of markers expressions.

Chapter 3

Results and discussion

3.1 Metabolomics as clustering benchmark

All frameworks used to predict fluxomics face the challenge of benchmarking due to technical difficulties in directly measuring metabolic fluxes at the genome-wide level to be used as ground truth. To overcome this problem, in this work, I used intracellular metabolomics as an evaluation benchmark to quantify the level of agreement of the computationally derived fluxomics with expected metabolic phenotypes.

Intracellular metabolomics describes metabolic profiles of cancer cells by measuring the actual concentration of metabolites (reactants) within a sample. Even if a specific enzyme is overexpressed in a cell, the absence of the associated metabolite, the reactant, reduces the overall reaction fluxes. It is better suited as a benchmark for evaluating the goodness of flux predictions because it is not directly used during the computation of fluxomics datasets. On the contrary, predicted fluxes are directly dependent from the transcriptomics and RAs datasets. Specifically, INTEGRATE uses the RNA-seq to compute the RASs, which in turn are used to create the cell-specific models that define the feasible regions that I sampled to obtain all the flux-derived statistics. Instead, scFEA directly uses the reads counts to predict flux distributions.

To obtain the metabolic clusters based on intracellular metabolomics to be used as a sort of ground truth, I tested different clustering techniques and hyperparameters. Table 3.1 presents the best clustering settings obtained using five different internal evaluation metrics. All metrics, except for the Davies-Bouldin index, indicated the presence of two clusters. The Silhouette index, with a medium-low value of 0.30, and the Calinski-Harabasz index both identified the same clustering setting, performed by K-means with $K = 2$. Figure 3.1 displays the clustering selected by the Silhouette index, shown through both PCA and UMAP representations. The assigned classes are quite unbalanced, with 64.71% of cells assigned to Cluster 0 and 35.29%

assigned to Cluster 1. The clustering with the highest Silhouette value was selected as the metabolic benchmark.

Although the biological interpretation of the two clusters goes beyond the aim of this thesis, to further verify that the two clusters correspond to distinct metabolic phenotypes I performed a marker analysis. Figure A.1 shows a heatmap representing the biomarkers identified using the Wilcoxon rank test between the two assigned labels. The dimensions of each cluster/group were scaled between 0 and 1 using the min-max scaler to facilitate the comparison of marker expressions across different groups. The heatmap colors indicate the metabolite concentrations within each cluster, with the matrix columns representing top-ranked metabolites and the rows corresponding to individual cells. Overall, both clusters are characterized by a set of highly expressed metabolites: Methionine and Leucine for cluster 0, and Uridine monophosphate (UMP) and Adenosine monophosphate (AMP) for cluster 1.

Figures A.2, A.3, A.4, illustrate the composition of the two clusters in terms of cell metadata, including respectively histology, pathology, and primary site. The majority of carcinoma samples were assigned to cluster 0, while cluster 1 is characterized by lymphoid neoplasms and hematopoietic neoplasms. These last two histologies refer to blood, or liquid, cancers that are likely to differentiate from solid tumors, as happened in [55]. Regarding pathology, no significant polarization of the two clusters was identified. Lastly, the primary site panel again shows a well-defined separation between liquid (lymphoid and hematopoietic tissues) and solid tumors.

Table 3.1: Best clustering settings for metabolomics.

Metric	Value	Clusters	Scaling	Algorithm
Distortion	216.02	2	Minmax	HDBSCAN
Silhouette	0.30	2	Minmax	K-means
Calinski-Harabasz	214.30	2	Minmax	K-means
Davies-Bouldin	1.00	7	Minmax	Agglomerative
DBCW	0.21	2	Minmax	HDBSCAN

Figure 3.1: Metabolomics clustering selected by Silhouette = 0.30: PCA and UMAP representation.

3.2 Transcriptomics and metabolomics share similar metabolic phenotypes

Transcriptomics regulates metabolism and reaction fluxes through transcriptional control, which relies on the expression levels of genes encoding specific enzymes responsible for reaction catalysis. However, metabolism is influenced by other factors such as post-transcriptional, post-translational and metabolic controls. Metabolomics measures the concentration of metabolites, the reaction reactants, within the cell and even if a reaction enzyme is over-expressed, the lack of the necessary metabolites reduces the reaction flux anyway. It is interesting to analyze the overlap between the metabolic subpopulations identified by transcriptomics and metabolomics. Given the metabolomics benchmark identified in the previous section, a comparison was performed with the clusterings derived from the RNA-seq matrix. The concordance level between these two omics in capturing cells heterogeneity is crucial, as they are the only two omics derived from experimental analysis rather than in silico methods.

Table 3.2 presents the best clustering results, obtained through grid-search, of RNA-seq data restricted to metabolic genes, evaluated through external metrics with respect to the benchmark. All metrics, except for homogeneity, indicated that the best clustering was achieved using the Leiden algorithm with two clusters and input data scaled by the Minmax scaler. The discrepancy in homogeneity is likely due to its bias towards a higher number of clusters in an attempt to identify purer groups. Generally, the NMI provides a better summary of homogeneity and completeness. The highest NMI is equal to 0.42, indicating a discrete overlap of the metabolic subpopulations identified by transcriptomics and metabolomics (see Figure 3.2).

Table 3.2: Best RNA-seq clusterings with respect to metabolomics benchmark.

Metric	Value	Clusters	Scaling	Algorithm
Homogeneity	0.53	36	Standard	Leiden
Completeness	0.43	2	Minmax	Leiden
NMI	0.42	2	Minmax	Leiden
AMI	0.55	2	Minmax	Leiden
ARI	0.42	2	Minmax	Leiden

Figure 3.2: Clustering of RNA-seq metabolic genes selected by highest NMI with intracellular metabolomics (NMI=0.42): a) RNA-seq PCA colored by metabolomics labels. b) RNA-seq UMAP colored by metabolomics labels. c) Metabolomics PCA colored by RNA-seq labels. d) Metabolomics UMAP colored by RNA-seq labels.

3.3 INTEGRATE fluxomics does not reflect metabolic profiles

The clusterings of predicted fluxes generated through the INTEGRATE pipeline, as well as all derived omics data such as mean, median, FBA and sensitivity analysis, were compared with the metabolomics benchmark and RNA-seq to numerically evaluate the degree of coherence between them. This comparison is crucial to determine if this constraint-based integration framework, which involves in silico experiments, aligns with the metabolomic phenotypes observed in laboratory settings.

For a given omic, the clustering with the highest NMI against the metabolomic benchmark was selected as the reference solution. This clustering, defined by a combination of clustering algorithm, scaling, and various hyperparameters, was then compared with all other omics, selected in the same manner. A brief summary of the INTEGRATE-derived omics is provided below:

- **RAS:** The Reaction Activity Score is computed for each reaction and cell line by the INTEGRATE framework. It serves as an intermediary step for integrating RNA-seq data into a constraint-based model.
- **pFBA:** Parsimonious Flux Balance Analysis is an extension of the standard FBA that aims to minimize the total flux through the network. The biomass reaction was selected as the objective function.
- **Sensitivity analysis:** The knockout of a model reaction from the stoichiometric matrix S enables the analysis of the effect of such deletion by performing Flux Balance Analysis (FBA). The sensitivity coefficient is the fraction of Biomass flux preserved after a reaction deletion.
- **Mean, mode, and median of sampled fluxes:** These three statistics were used to summarize the distributions of the fluxes sampled by CBS and CHRR.
- **Fluxes correlation with biomass:** The Spearman correlation coefficient was computed to compare the sampled fluxes of each cell line with the sampled Biomass, for both CHRR and CBS.

Figure 3.3 displays the NMI scores for the INTEGRATE-related omics derived from the RNA-seq matrix. All the clustering hyperparameters are detailed in Table A.2 in the Appendix. Surprisingly, all predicted fluxomics demonstrated a very poor ability to represent actual metabolic profiles. In fact, low NMIs were observed between fluxomics and metabolomics. For example, the mean fluxes sampled by CBS obtained an NMI of 0.10, while CHRR achieved an NMI of 0.09. As previously discussed, a moderate NMI

is observed between metabolomics and RNA-seq, equal to 0.42. Similarly, the RAS matrix, which is closely dependent on transcriptomics, recorded an NMI of 0.40 with the benchmark. The dependency between RNA-seq and RAS computed by INTEGRATE is confirmed by an NMI of 0.81. Thus, INTEGRATE preserves the metabolic phenotypes of the RNA-seq matrix even in the RAS, which are produced by exploiting the GPR rules of the model.

I investigated whether the problem was related to the loss of information when using summary statistics, such as the mean of all sampled flux distributions. However, both sensitivity analysis and pFBA also obtained very low NMIs of 0.09 and 0.05, respectively. Additionally, the NMI between clustering the mean and median of CBS fluxes is 0.49, while the NMI between the mean and median of CHRR fluxes is 0.75. This indicates that the summary statistics are quite overlapping on the metabolic subpopulations.

I verified the robustness of the NMI to discard the hypothesis of its inadequacy, in comparison to using ARI or AMI. Specifically, the Pearson correlation coefficients of ARI and AMI with respect to NMI are 0.97 and 0.99, respectively. Furthermore, these three measures selected the exact same clustering setting for a given omic in 71% of the cases. For completeness, Table 3.3 shows the ARI and AMI scores with respect to metabolomics.

metabolomics	1.00												
rna_seq_metabolic	0.42	1.00											
ras	0.40	0.81	1.00										
pFBA	0.05	0.11	0.10	1.00									
sensitivity_analysis	0.09	0.12	0.11	0.09	1.00								
CBS_mean	0.10	0.17	0.17	0.29	0.12	1.00							
CBS_mode	0.08	0.11	0.11	0.22	0.08	0.28	1.00						
CBS_median	0.08	0.13	0.12	0.21	0.13	0.49	0.34	1.00					
correlation_CBS	0.07	0.11	0.11	0.24	0.13	0.35	0.25	0.46	1.00				
CHRR_mean	0.09	0.13	0.13	0.27	0.11	0.57	0.32	0.44	0.32	1.00			
CHRR_mode	0.08	0.11	0.11	0.21	0.14	0.53	0.33	0.60	0.43	0.53	1.00		
CHRR_median	0.09	0.12	0.11	0.23	0.12	0.56	0.31	0.51	0.34	0.75	0.60	1.00	
correlation_CHRR	0.08	0.13	0.12	0.13	0.12	0.10	0.05	0.08	0.12	0.10	0.08	0.10	1.00
	metabolomics	rna_seq_metabolic	ras	pFBA	sensitivity_analysis	CBS_mean	CBS_mode	CBS_median	correlation_CBS	CHRR_mean	CHRR_mode	CHRR_median	correlation_CHRR

Figure 3.3: NMI computed between omics clusterings having the highest overlap with metabolomics.

Table 3.3: ARI and AMI best scores for INTEGRATE-related omics against the benchmark metabolomics.

Omic	ARI	AMI
RNA-seq metabolic	0.55	0.42
RAS	0.53	0.40
pFBA	0.06	0.05
Sensitivity analysis	0.07	0.06
CBS mean	0.08	0.09
CBS mode	0.08	0.07
CBS median	0.09	0.06
Correlation CBS	0.05	0.06
CHRR mean	0.10	0.09
CHRR mode	0.10	0.06
CHRR median	0.11	0.08
Correlation CHRR	0.12	0.08

All in all, these results indicate that predicted fluxomics show a poor ability to represent actual metabolic profiles. This surprising outcome may stem from a limitation in the INTEGRATE framework’s ability to accurately constrain feasible regions based on the RAS matrix. Under these conditions, well-clustered genetic profiles could have been compromised when integrated into the constraint-based framework, leading to lower-quality flux predictions.

To test INTEGRATE’s reliability, the generated feasible regions were compared to quantify their similarity. Specifically, 100 samples were randomly drawn from both the CHRR and CBS batches, and for each pair of cells c_1 and c_2 , the percentage of c_1 samples feasible for the c_2 model, and vice versa, was calculated. This resulted in a matrix M of size 513×513 , where $M_{i,j}$ represents the percentage of c_i samples feasible for c_j . The matrix diagonal, which contains 100%, was excluded from the analysis. In the case of CBS, over 90% of the cell pairs had a feasibility score of less than 10%. Conversely, in the case of CHRR, all cell pairs had a feasibility percentage of less than 6%.

Based on these findings, the initial hypothesis was rejected; thus, INTEGRATE is not the primary cause of the low NMIs observed, as the feasible regions differ sufficiently from one another. Consequently, the cause must lie outside the INTEGRATE framework, specifically within the RNA-seq matrix.

3.4 MAGIC mitigates RNA-seq noise

Single-cell transcriptomics suffers from the dropout phenomenon, where expressed genes are not correctly detected due to the small sample size under analysis. In fact, it is well known that only a small portion (typically between 5% and 15%) of each cell's transcriptome is captured [45]. Limitations in detecting genes with low expression levels can lead to a phenomenon known as "dropout," where expressed genes fail to be detected. The associated transcriptomic matrices are highly sparse with many false negatives. For these reasons, algorithms such as MAGIC [8] are used to mitigate the noise in such matrices and extract the original transcriptional profiles.

In this study, I dealt with bulk samples, where transcriptomics are measured from a group of cells from the same tissue. This technology does not usually require denoising preprocessing *a priori* because high levels of noise are typically not expected. There was no reason to apply the MAGIC algorithm to the RNA-seq matrix due to the nature of the transcriptomics data, coming from bulk samples, and because the metabolic models revealed that all cells were growing, so no issues with essential genes were present. However, the low concordance levels registered between the predicted fluxomics and the metabolomic benchmarks suggested the need to improve the quality of the RNA-seq matrix. Consequently, MAGIC was applied to the RNA-seq matrix to enhance its quality for flux predictions.

The transcriptomics matrix was scaled using a logarithmic scale as suggested by [46] and then processed with the MAGIC algorithm as described in the previous chapter. MAGIC reduced the matrix sparsity percentage from 43% to 0.02% in the case of the full RNA-seq matrix and from 0.08% to 0% in the case of the RNA-seq matrix containing ENGRO2 genes only, i.e., metabolic genes only. Figure 3.4 shows the full scaled RNA-seq matrix before and after applying MAGIC, where rows correspond to cells and columns to genes. It is evident that the second matrix has higher expression values with fewer blue spots, which correspond to lowly expressed genes.

Figure 3.4: RNA-seq matrix scaled between zero and one: a) Before MAGIC
b) After MAGIC

Moreover, MAGIC increased the correlation between the RAS matrix, computed within the INTEGRATE pipeline, and the fluxes derived from CBS and CHRR. Figure 3.5 illustrates the distributions of Spearman correlation coefficients (absolute values) calculated for the mean and median fluxes of CHRR and CBS, with and without MAGIC denoising applied to the RNA-seq matrix. The violin plots for the MAGIC-enhanced versions (first two plots from the left in both panels) show higher correlations with distributions characterized by longer tails. A higher correlation indicates that the reaction scores more accurately translate into constraints within the feasible region, meaning the fluxes are more likely to reflect the integrated reaction scores in the INTEGRATE framework. For instance, a reaction with genes exhibiting low expression values will result in a low RAS, and with MAGIC, it is more likely to yield a correspondingly low flux.

Figure 3.5: Distribution of Spearman coefficients, as absolute values, between RAS and sampled fluxes by CHRR and CBS, both with and without MAGIC denoiser: a) Fluxes mean b) Fluxes median.

Tables 3.4 and 3.5 present the optimal clustering settings for the original RNA-seq data and the denoised RNA-seq data, respectively, after selecting only metabolic genes (ENGRO2 genes). It is evident that all internal evaluation metrics improved after applying MAGIC to the gene expression matrix. Specifically, Table 3.5 shows a medium-high Silhouette score of 0.59 and a DBCV score of 0.80. However, the five different settings do not agree on the number of clusters within the dataset. For example, the Silhouette score is associated with eight clusters, while the DBCV score corresponds to just four. The higher internal metrics can be attributed to MAGIC’s ability to enhance similarities between cells by repairing missing genes, potentially caused by experimental noise, through the diffusion process. This results in denser clusters being identified.

Table 3.4: Best clustering settings for RNA-seq restricted to metabolic genes.

Metric	Value	Clusters	Scaling	Algorithm
Distortion	434.46	2	Minmax	HDBSCAN
Silhouette	0.09	6	Minmax	Leiden
Calinski-Harabasz	40.00	2	Minmax	K-means
Davies-Bouldin	1.53	9	Standard	Agglomerative
DBCV	0.02	2	Minmax	HDBSCAN

Table 3.5: Best clustering settings for RNA-seq restricted to metabolic genes and processed with MAGIC.

Metric	Value	Clusters	Scaling	Algorithm
Distortion	218.88	29	Minmax	Leiden
Silhouette	0.59	8	Standard	Agglomerative
Calinski-Harabasz	800.94	21	Minmax	Leiden
Davies-Bouldin	0.49	11	Minmax	Leiden
DBCV	0.80	4	Minmax	Agglomerative

Figure 3.6 illustrates the biomarker heatmap identified using the Wilcoxon rank test between the two assigned labels. The heatmap colors indicate gene expression levels within each cluster, with the matrix columns representing top-ranked genes and the rows corresponding to individual cells. In general, the biomarkers seem well differentiated, but there is a significant label imbalance, with clusters 1 and 2 containing only a small percentage of the cells.

Figure 3.6: Scaled heatmap of the metabolic genes RNA-seq matrix markers processed by MAGIC (clustering selected by DBCV). Columns represent genes, rows are associated to cells and colors are proportional to genes expression level.

To ensure that no numerical artifacts were introduced into the RNA-seq matrix, I compared the concordance level between the two transcriptomics matrices (before and after MAGIC processing) with metabolomics. The best RNA-seq clusterings with respect to external evaluation metrics with metabolomics are shown by Table 3.2, while Table 3.6 presents the same evaluation metrics after applying MAGIC. Again, all metrics indicated that two clusters were the best option with the K-medoids algorithm, except for homogeneity, which preferred 29 clusters with the Leiden algorithm. For both versions of the RNA-seq data, a moderate level of coherence with the metabolomics benchmark was observed: 0.42 before MAGIC and 0.41 after MAGIC.

Moreover, the Silhouette score of the clustering selected by highest NMI improved from 0.08 without MAGIC to 0.38 with MAGIC because MAGIC enhances similarities between cells through the diffusion process, thereby reducing intra-cluster distances. However, no significant changes were observed in the external evaluation metrics.

The consistency of NMI between RNA-seq and metabolomics, which remained largely unchanged, validates the effectiveness of the MAGIC algorithm. This indicates, as stated by [8], that MAGIC did not introduce numerical artifacts into the RNA-seq matrix, as the metabolic profiles remained consistent in both cases, maintaining the same level of agreement

with the benchmark.

Table 3.6: Best RNA-seq clusterings processed by MAGIC with respect to metabolomics benchmark.

Metric	Value	Clusters	Scaling	Algorithm
Homogeneity	0.52	29	Minmax	Leiden
Completeness	0.41	2	Standard	K-medoids
NMI	0.41	2	Minmax	K-medoids
AMI	0.41	2	Minmax	K-medoids
ARI	0.54	2	Minmax	K-medoids

3.5 MAGIC improves fluxomics prediction

Figures 3.7 display the NMI scores for the INTEGRATE-related omics, where the RNA-seq matrix was processed by MAGIC before being input into the INTEGRATE pipeline. All the clustering hyperparameters are shown in Table A.3 in the Appendix. Significant differences are observed in the NMIs between the predicted fluxomics and the metabolomics benchmark. For example, in the case of CBS, the mean fluxes increased from 0.10 to 0.30, the median from 0.08 to 0.39, the mode from 0.08 to 0.32 and the Biomass correlation from 0.07 to 0.39. Similarly, for CHRR, the mean went from 0.09 to 0.33, the median from 0.09 to 0.32, the mode from 0.08 to 0.29 and the Biomass correlation from 0.08 to 0.28. The NMI improved even for omics not derived from sampled fluxes, such as pFBA, from 0.05 to 0.23, and sensitivity analysis, from 0.09 to 0.26. Higher NMIs are also found between different omics, indicating a higher general overlap. For example, the NMI between the CHRR mode and CBS mean increased from 0.53 to 0.96, and between the CHRR median and CBS mean, it increased from 0.56 to 0.94. This suggests that the preprocessing of RNA-seq data with MAGIC significantly enhances the ability of predicted fluxomics to represent actual metabolic profiles and improves the agreement between different omic datasets.

INTEGRATE generated constraint-based models and enabled the computation of all fluxes. The denoising activity of the MAGIC algorithm led to higher coherence scores. However, the RNA-seq and RAS matrices maintained relatively consistent NMIs against metabolomics regardless of MAGIC. As previously explained, the RNA-seq matrix exhibited high sparsity without denoising, while after MAGIC, the percentage of non-expressed genes significantly decreased due to the algorithm's diffusion process. Moreover, MAGIC preserved the original information in the RNA-seq matrix, evidenced by a stable NMI coefficient with metabolomics. This indicates that adjusting the matrix to remove noise does not alter the genetic information it contains, nor does it affect the reaction scores in the RAS matrix. However, significant differences are observed in predicted fluxomics. This happened because new information emerges from intersecting the flux constraints, where the flux of one reaction can influence another when computing a feasible sample. If the RNA-seq matrix contains substantial noise, a low-quality feasible region is created. In summary, MAGIC enhances data coherence by reducing noise and preserving genetic information. Its effects on flux predictions highlight the importance of noise-free inputs for accurately defining the feasible metabolic space and deriving meaningful solutions.

metabolomics	1.00												
rna_seq_metabolic	0.41	1.00											
ras	0.42	0.89	1.00										
pFBA	0.23	0.43	0.43	1.00									
sensitivity_analysis	0.26	0.56	0.58	0.41	1.00								
CBS_mean	0.30	0.59	0.57	0.52	0.56	1.00							
CBS_mode	0.32	0.67	0.65	0.50	0.57	0.85	1.00						
CBS_median	0.39	0.64	0.68	0.50	0.42	0.58	0.68	1.00					
correlation_CBS	0.39	0.64	0.68	0.50	0.42	0.58	0.68	1.00	1.00				
CHRR_mean	0.33	0.53	0.56	0.45	0.37	0.66	0.74	0.80	0.80	1.00			
CHRR_mode	0.29	0.58	0.55	0.52	0.54	0.96	0.88	0.58	0.58	0.65	1.00		
CHRR_median	0.32	0.62	0.61	0.53	0.56	0.94	0.79	0.62	0.62	0.62	0.92	1.00	
correlation_CHRR	0.28	0.46	0.50	0.37	0.35	0.50	0.47	0.63	0.63	0.53	0.49	0.52	1.00
	metabolomics	rna_seq_metabolic	ras	pFBA	sensitivity_analysis	CBS_mean	CBS_mode	CBS_median	correlation_CBS	CHRR_mean	CHRR_mode	CHRR_median	correlation_CHRR

Figure 3.7: NMI between omics with MAGIC denoising.

Previously, it was shown that INTEGRATE generated feasible regions with a minimal percentage of shared feasible solutions, supporting the hypothesis that low-quality fluxes are due to the RNA-seq matrix. To reinforce this hypothesis, Figures 3.8 and 3.9 show 1000 random samples generated by CHRR for five different cancer cells, before and after MAGIC respectively. It is clear that in both cases, the samples are well-clustered and respect the ground truth of their respective cells. However, well-clustered samples do not necessarily imply that fluxes strictly represent real metabolic phenotypes. In fact, poor NMI scores were found without MAGIC. In summary, the responsibility for low-quality fluxes lies with the noise in the RNA-seq matrix, which is amplified when combining gene expression into the constraint-based model.

Figure 3.8: 1000 random samples generated by CHRR of five different cells, coloured by cell partnership: a) PCA. b) UMAP.

Figure 3.9: 1000 random samples generated by CHRR of five different cells, coloured by cell partnership after RNA-seq denoising: a) PCA. b) UMAP.

Figures 3.10 and 3.11 show the impact of MAGIC on each omic's NMI and silhouette scores, respectively. Although the RNA-seq and RAS did not improve their NMI scores, a significant increase in the silhouette score was observed, going from 0.09 to 0.38. This indicates that the quality of the clusters has improved in terms of inter- and intra-cluster distances because of the diffusion process that enhances similarities among already near cells. For all other omics, it is clear that both the NMI against metabolomics and the quality of the clusters (as indicated by higher silhouette scores) improved after applying MAGIC. This demonstrates that MAGIC not only enhances data coherence but also significantly improves clustering quality across different omics data, while maintaining stable benchmark concordance for RNA-seq and RAS.

Figure 3.10: Barplot of omics NMI against the metabolomics benchmark, both with and without MAGIC denoising.

Figure 3.11: Barplot of clusterings silhouette, selected by NMI against the metabolomics benchmark, both with and without MAGIC denoising.

Among the summary statistics computed for the fluxes sampled by CBS and CHRR, the median and Biomass correlation were found to be optimal for CBS (NMI = 0.39), while the mean should be preferred for CHRR (NMI = 0.33). Beginning with CBS, as discussed by [1], the final marginal distributions generated by CBS approximate a discrete probability distribution due to sampling a few values multiple times from finite feasible region vertices. The median was identified as the optimal statistic because it is less sensitive to outliers that might adversely affect other statistics, such as the average fluxes. In contrast, CHRR samples the entire feasible region using algorithms, which is less likely to produce bimodal distributions, as indicated by [1]. The mean was found to be the best choice for CHRR due to the presence of relatively uniform marginal distributions. Both CHRR and CBS statistics showed high NMIs between their mode and median statistics, suggesting that both sampling strategies captured similar metabolic profiles. However, summary statistics alone may not be exhaustive. Therefore, I clustered real fluxes too, as discussed in the next section.

3.6 CHRR outperforms CBS in samples clustering

It is useful to investigate the relationship between metabolomics and fluxes sampled by CBS and CHRR without relying on any statistics that might excessively simplify the flux distributions. For each cell, I randomly selected 50 samples only, and I used the mini-batch K-means to reduce the clustering computational cost ($50 \cdot 513 = 25,650$ samples). To validate the subsampling, the Wilcoxon–Mann–Whitney test was performed to compare the subsampling to the original flux distribution of each reaction, which contained 10,000 values. This non-parametric test is not influenced by differences in sample size between the two distributions. Table 3.7 shows the average percentage of reactions where the test found a significant difference from the original distribution with $\alpha = 0.05$. On average, CBS registered 1.62% of rejected reactions without MAGIC and 1.96% with MAGIC. CHRR registered 5.17% without MAGIC and 4.95% with MAGIC. The low values suggested a sufficient reliability of the subsamples.

At this point, each cell was represented by 50 samples, but the metabolomics benchmark assigned just one label per sample. To compare the two assignments through NMI, each cell was assigned to the cluster containing the majority of its samples. For example, if cell_{*i*} has 26 samples in cluster 0, then the cell is assigned to cluster 0. Figures 3.12 and 3.13 show the NMI for the sampled fluxes without and with MAGIC, respectively. CHRR samples NMI with metabolomics shifted from 0.05 to 0.25 without and with MAGIC, respectively. However, CBS did not improve as well, shifting from 0.01 to just 0.05. Eventually, CHRR outperformed CBS in coherence with the benchmark, despite this phenomenon not being visible when dealing with summary statistics.

Table 3.7: The Wilcoxon–Mann–Whitney test was used to compare the subsampled fluxes against the original flux distribution for each cell and sampling algorithm. This table reports the average percentage of rejected reactions for each sampling algorithm.

Algorithm	Magic	Rejected reactions
CBS	No	1.62%
CHRR	No	5.17%
CBS	Yes	1.96%
CHRR	Yes	4.95%

Figure 3.12: CBS, CHRR and metabolomics NMI without MAGIC denoising.

Figure 3.13: CBS, CHRR and metabolomics NMI with MAGIC denoising.

As previously explained and discussed in depth by [1], the final marginal distributions generated by CBS approximate a discrete probability distribution with multiple modalities. In contrast, CHRR samples the entire feasible region and is less likely to produce multi-modal distributions, but it tends to generate uniform and Gaussian-like distributions. The most probable explanation for the superior performance of CHRR when dealing with actual fluxes rather than statistics is that summary statistics mitigate the multi-modal distributions of CBS samples.

When dealing with CBS fluxes, they could be likely to cluster within the modalities. For example, Figure 3.14 shows the density function of the same reaction r sampled by CBS from two different cells c_1 and c_2 to generate two flux distributions r_1 and r_2 . These distributions were specifically created to have the same density peaks but with different magnitudes. When clustering, the algorithm splits the samples of c_1 and c_2 based on the modalities they belong to, rather than considering the distribution as a whole. Moreover, it may happen that samples of c_1 and c_2 are grouped together because they belong to the same modality, even though the cells differ in terms of flux distributions.

Figure 3.14: Density distribution functions of an hypothetical reaction r sampled by CBS from cells c_1 and c_2 to generate r_1 and r_2 .

The clustering of CHRR fluxes, using MAGIC, showed the highest NMI with metabolomics when $K=2$ and minmax scaling were applied as preprocessing steps. Figure 3.15 indicates that 67.64% of the cells had all their samples within a single cluster (100% being the highest cell partnership to a cluster), suggesting that the majority of the cells sampled by CHRR and processed by MAGIC had an extremely strong polarization towards the computed clusters. Figure 3.16 illustrates the PCA and UMAP of the CHRR

fluxes, colored by the clusters assigned by mini-batch K-means (panels a and b), and similarly for the metabolomics, colored by the fluxes clusters (panels c and d). Even with an NMI of 0.25, a distinct pattern emerges when the metabolomics data points are colored by the labels identified by the clustered fluxes.

Figure 3.15: This figure shows the distribution of the highest partnership percentage for each cell. The x-axis represents the highest partnership percentage of a cell to a cluster, while the y-axis shows the absolute frequency of the discretized percentages, ranging from 0 to 513.

Figure 3.16: CHRR fluxes selected by highest NMI with metabolomics: a) PCA of sampled fluxes colored by cluster partnership. b) UMAP of sampled fluxes colored by cluster partnership. c) PCA of metabolomics colored by fluxes labels (a cell is assigned to one of the two clusters depending on which cluster contains the majority of its samples). d) UMAP of metabolomics colored by fluxes labels.

3.7 scFEA as promising integration framework

Single-cell flux estimation analysis (scFEA) is a novel computational method used to estimate the relative rate of metabolic flux at single-cell resolution from single cell RNA-seq data. It distinguishes from constraint-based integration methods, such as INTEGRATE, because it directly uses gene expression data to predict fluxes without defining a feasible region to be analyzed through sampling or optimization techniques. A multilayer fully connected network is used to model the nonlinear dependency between gene expression and reaction rates and their correlation is maximized. At the same time, flux imbalance is minimized between modules.

In this thesis, I used scFEA on bulk samples to benchmark its integration performance, as was done with INTEGRATE. Figures 3.17 and 3.18 show the NMI of scFEA against the metabolomics benchmark and RNA-seq data restricted to metabolic genes and RAS, both with and without MAGIC, respectively. Similar to RNA-seq and RAS, the NMI of scFEA with the benchmark is not significantly influenced by the application of MAGIC. Specifically, its NMI increases marginally from 0.38 without MAGIC to 0.40 with MAGIC. However, substantial improvements are observed in the NMIs of scFEA against RAS and RNA-seq when the denoising algorithm is applied, with the NMI increasing from 0.60 to 0.89 for RNA-seq and from 0.54 to 0.83 for RAS, respectively.

Figure 3.17: Metabolomics, scFEA, RNA-seq and RAS NMI without MAGIC denoising.

Figure 3.18: Metabolomics, scFEA, RNA-seq and RAS NMI with MAGIC denoising.

scFEA fluxomics was capable of mitigating the RNA-seq noise without the need for the MAGIC algorithm. This is clearly demonstrated by Figures 3.19 (without MAGIC) and 3.20 (with MAGIC), where scFEA leads in terms of NMI with the metabolomics benchmark among the set of fluxes-related omics. The differences in terms of NMIs between scFEA and INTEGRATE are significant only when MAGIC is not applied to the transcriptomics matrix, thus when INTEGRATE is unable to mitigate the transcriptomics noise. These two figures show that pFBA and sensitivity analysis were the two worst omics regarding metabolomics coherence both with and without MAGIC preprocessing, and they were outperformed by summary statistics of INTEGRATE fluxomics and scFEA naturally.

scFEA effectively discriminates noise in the RNA-seq data and better represents the metabolomic profile of the bulk samples thanks to its innovative approach based on ANNs for maximizing the correlation between gene expression and flux rates. Moreover, scFEA produces a single vector containing the predicted fluxes for each cell, avoiding the need for subsequent computations like FBA, sampling, or summary statistics. scFEA is a prominent integration method that aims to overcome the limitations of constraint-based steady-state integration frameworks, but it is not without its drawbacks. First, it computes the fluxes of a restricted set of reactions, leaving out some relevant reactions such as Biomass. Secondly, it is still not

possible to integrate growth medium details into the loss function or to use a customized metabolic model to shape the metabolic pathways.

Figure 3.19: Predicted fluxomics NMIs with metabolomics: scFEA and INTEGRATE.

Figure 3.20: Predicted fluxomics NMIs with metabolomics (MAGIC applied over RNA-seq): scFEA and INTEGRATE.

Chapter 4

Conclusions

Metabolism is intricately linked to nearly all cellular processes, making it a key indicator of a cell's or organism's physiological state. A deep understanding of cancer cell metabolism, or pathological conditions in general, can reveal hidden features that could be exploited to combat these cells. Integrating omics data, such as transcriptomics and metabolomics, within metabolic models allows for the prediction of reaction fluxes by characterizing the metabolism. Unfortunately, evaluating the performance of integration methods is challenging because the ground truth of fluxes is typically limited to a small set of reactions due to high costs and technical difficulties. The objective of this thesis is to develop an evaluation pipeline for integration methods to address the benchmarking issue and leverage high-throughput data to characterize metabolic phenotypes for further biological research. This thesis is based on the assumption that cells with similar metabolite concentrations are likely to exhibit similar fluxes and, consequently, similar metabolic profiles.

Transcriptomics data from 513 different cancer bulk samples were obtained from The Cancer Cell Line Encyclopedia (CCLE) Project and integrated using two methods: INTEGRATE, a constraint-based steady-state method, and scFEA, a framework based on artificial neural networks designed to overcome the limitations of constraint-based methods. Subsequently, I used intracellular metabolomics of the same set of cells to establish the evaluation benchmark for the predicted fluxes. Specifically, the metabolic cancer phenotypes identified through cluster analysis were compared to those selected by the benchmarks to evaluate their concordance using external metrics such as NMI. INTEGRATE generated cell-specific metabolic models that were sampled by two sampling algorithms: CHRR, which explores the internal feasible region, and CBS, which focuses on the corners of the feasible region. I used summary statistics, such as mean and median, to condense the information gathered through flux sampling. On the other hand, scFEA directly generated a compact flux distribution for each cell. Special attention

was paid to the hyperparameter optimization of the clustering algorithms (K-means, K-medoids, Agglomerative, HDBSCAN, and Leiden) and the preprocessing of the RNA-seq matrix with the MAGIC denoiser.

The cluster analysis of the intracellular metabolomics robustly revealed the presence of two subpopulations. This result is supported by optimal values in several internal evaluation metrics (Distortion, Silhouette, Calinski-Harabasz, and DBCV). The final benchmark selection was based on the highest Silhouette score of 0.30 (see Figure 3.1), identified by the K-means algorithm. The clusters are imbalanced, with 64.71% of cells in Cluster 0 and 35.29% in Cluster 1.

Metabolism is regulated by both genes encoding enzymes that drive reactions and by intracellular metabolite concentrations necessary for metabolic fluxes. This thesis revealed that, within the analyzed dataset, transcriptomics and metabolomics exhibit similar metabolic phenotypes, as evidenced by an NMI of 0.42 between their clusters. Amongst the RNA-seq clusterings, the one with the highest NMI, characterized by two clusters and identified using the Leiden algorithm, was selected (see Figure 3.2).

Despite the high level of coherence between metabolomics and transcriptomics, the fluxomics predicted by INTEGRATE did not accurately reflect the metabolic phenotypes identified by the benchmark, as evidenced by low NMIs across all flux statistics (see Figure 3.3). The fluxes showed low NMI values with respect to both intracellular metabolomics and even RNA-seq and RAS matrix where a strong dependence is trivially defined by the INTEGRATE algorithm. However, this discrepancy was not attributable to limitations of the INTEGRATE method itself. In fact, INTEGRATE generated 513 distinct feasible regions, with less than 10% overlap for CBS and 6% overlap for CHRR in shared feasible solutions, demonstrating that the polytopes derived from the integrated RNA-seq data were well-characterized. The real cause of such poor results was the noise contained in the RNA-seq matrix.

Originally designed for single-cell RNA-seq, which is characterized by high dropout rates, the MAGIC algorithm reduced the sparsity percentage from 43% to 0.02% for the full gene matrix and from 0.08% to 0% for the matrix containing only metabolic genes (see Figure 3.4). MAGIC did not introduce numerical artifacts, as the transcriptomics NMI with the metabolomics benchmark remained consistent while improving clustering quality by creating more compact clusters. This improvement is attributed to MAGIC's ability to enhance similarities and differences between cells through the diffusion process in the K-NN graph. Graphical examples are shown in Figures 3.8 and 3.9 where, even without MAGIC, well-clustered fluxes are shown. Eventually, the low fluxomics NMIs were primarily due to noise present in the RNA-seq matrix. Although MAGIC was not applied, a sufficient NMI was still observed between transcriptomics and metabolomics benchmarks. However, the fluxes remained significantly influenced by transcriptomic noise. This

issue arises because the flux solutions are derived from a combination of multiple constraints based on the original RNA-seq matrix, and the presence of even small errors is amplified, resulting in poor-quality fluxomics.

For CBS, the mean fluxes increased from 0.10 to 0.30, the median from 0.08 to 0.39, and the mode from 0.08 to 0.32. For CHRR, the mean went from 0.09 to 0.33, the median from 0.09 to 0.32, and the mode from 0.08 to 0.29. In general, the most promising fluxomics summary statistics are the fluxes median and Biomass correlation for CBS (NMIs = 0.39), and mode for CHRR (NMI = 0.33). Additionally, MAGIC improved cluster quality, leading to higher Silhouette scores as well (see Figures 3.11).

The denoiser effects were also clear over CHRR and CBS subsamples (50 flux samples per cell) where increased the NMI between benchmark and CHRR from 0.05 to 0.25 and 0.01 to 0.05 for CBS (see Figures 3.12 and 3.13). The CBS algorithm collected extremely poor results in both cases, while this did not happen in the case of flux summary statistics. The most probable hypothesis for such behavior is based on the fact that CBS distributions are likely to be multi-modal, as discussed by [1] and shown by 3.14, and thus the clustering algorithms might clusterize the modalities rather than the whole flux distribution.

scFEA, which produces a compact flux distribution for each cell, achieved an NMI of 0.38 with the raw RNA-seq matrix, outperforming INTEGRATE fluxomics, whose highest NMI was 0.10, achieved by the CBS mean. The differences between scFEA and INTEGRATE nearly disappeared when applying MAGIC. Specifically, scFEA achieved an NMI of 0.40, while INTEGRATE fluxomics closely followed with an NMI of 0.39, achieved by CBS median and Biomass correlation.

scFEA is immune to MAGIC effects due to its intrinsic algorithm structure, which is based on a loss function that maximizes the correlation between gene expression and fluxes. In essence, scFEA automatically performs the role of MAGIC. However, scFEA has some drawbacks. For example, it computes the fluxes of a restricted set of reactions, and it is not yet possible to use a customized metabolic model or growth medium to shape the metabolic pathway.

To summarize, the analyses I performed in this thesis demonstrated a moderate level of concordance between intracellular metabolomics and transcriptomics. These findings led to the proposal of a new evaluation pipeline for selecting the optimal integration framework based on metabolomics as benchmark. Initially, the INTEGRATE framework was damaged by noise in the transcriptomics matrix, resulting in low-quality fluxomics and consequently low concordance levels with both benchmarks and transcriptomics. However, the MAGIC algorithm significantly improved the performance of INTEGRATE fluxomics. On the other hand, scFEA proved to be extremely promising, acting effectively as a denoiser with its innovative approach that overcomes traditional constraint-based limitations, such as linear constraints

and steady state. Overall, neither INTEGRATE nor scFEA drastically outperformed the other in terms of NMI when using MAGIC. The final benchmarking pipeline was established by utilizing the best intracellular metabolomics clustering (in this case, the highest Silhouette score) to evaluate the subpopulations identified by all fluxomics datasets produced by integration methods like INTEGRATE and scFEA.

The identified clusters can be examined by expert life scientists to extract valuable insights about the biomarkers of each subpopulation. An example of such an operation is shown in the RNA-seq clustering, which revealed an interesting pattern based on cancer histology, with one group containing the majority of solid tumors and another group containing liquid ones. This is a known property of cancer cells, as discussed by [55].

Future research extensions may include the analysis of a wider range of integration frameworks, such as iMAT [15] and FASTCORE [16], to increase the robustness of the benchmarking pipeline. Additionally, more advanced methods for dimensionality reduction, such as ISOMAP [56] and Autoencoders [57], could be explored. Implementing classifiers to adjust clustering hyperparameters to optimize the concordance level with the benchmark is another promising avenue for future work.

The INTEGRATE pipeline and clustering comparison implemented in this thesis are going to be deployed in the Google Summer Of Code 2024, as this project was selected by the National Resource for Network Biology (NRNB) under the title: "COBRAXy: COBRA and MaREA4Galaxy". COBRAXy is going to be a new Galaxy tool [58] (Galaxy is an open-source, web-based platform for data-intensive biomedical research) that will extend the already existing MaREA4Galaxy [59] (a Galaxy tool that implements, amongst other things, the RAS computation and clustering). COBRAXy deploys the complete INTEGRATE pipeline: cell-specific COBRA models, flux sampling, summary flux statistics, clustering grid search and comparison.

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Appendix A

Supplementary figures and tables

A.1 PCA preprocessing

Table A.1: Selected principal components, based on 80% threshold over the explained cumulative variance, for each omic and scaling method.

Omic	Scaling	Dimensionality	Selected PCs
metabolomics	minmax	225	36
metabolomics	standard	225	39
metabolomics_ENGRO2	minmax	62	17
metabolomics_ENGRO2	standard	62	19
ras	minmax	245	60
ras	standard	245	70
rna_seq_total	minmax	46943	70
rna_seq_total	standard	46943	70
rna_seq_metabolic_genes	minmax	492	70
rna_seq_metabolic_genes	standard	492	70
ras_magic	minmax	245	7
ras_magic	standard	245	8
rna_seq_total_magic	minmax	46943	9
rna_seq_total_magic	standard	46943	9
rna_seq_metabolic_genes_magic	minmax	492	8
rna_seq_metabolic_genes_magic	standard	492	8

fluxes_CBS_mean	minmax	238	14
fluxes_CBS_mean	standard	238	18
fluxes_CBS_mode	minmax	206	27
fluxes_CBS_mode	standard	206	44
fluxes_CBS_median	minmax	217	19
fluxes_CBS_median	standard	217	31
fluxes_CBS	minmax	240	17
fluxes_CBS	standard	240	39
fluxes_CBS_mean_magic	minmax	238	4
fluxes_CBS_mean_magic	standard	238	5
fluxes_CBS_mode_magic	minmax	175	12
fluxes_CBS_mode_magic	standard	175	19
fluxes_CBS_median_magic	minmax	167	7
fluxes_CBS_median_magic	standard	167	10
fluxes_CBS_magic	minmax	238	18
fluxes_CBS_magic	standard	238	28
fluxes_CHRR_mean	minmax	238	13
fluxes_CHRR_mean	standard	238	16
fluxes_CHRR_mode	minmax	238	16
fluxes_CHRR_mode	standard	238	20
fluxes_CHRR_median	minmax	238	13
fluxes_CHRR_median	standard	238	15
fluxes_CHRR	minmax	238	21
fluxes_CHRR	standard	238	35
fluxes_CHRR_mean_magic	minmax	238	3
fluxes_CHRR_mean_magic	standard	238	4
fluxes_CHRR_mode_magic	minmax	238	5
fluxes_CHRR_mode_magic	standard	238	6
fluxes_CHRR_median_magic	minmax	238	3
fluxes_CHRR_median_magic	standard	238	4
fluxes_CHRR_magic	minmax	238	30
fluxes_CHRR_magic	standard	238	41
scFEA	minmax	70	25
scFEA	standard	70	30
scFEA_magic	minmax	70	7
scFEA_magic	standard	70	7
FBA	minmax	161	3
FBA	standard	161	7
FBA_magic	minmax	109	2
FBA_magic	standard	109	2
FVA	minmax	272	18

FVA	standard	272	22
FVA_magic	minmax	254	4
FVA_magic	standard	254	5
pFBA	minmax	161	3
pFBA	standard	161	7
pFBA_magic	minmax	109	2
pFBA_magic	standard	109	2
fluxes_CBS_stats_magic	minmax	727	6
fluxes_CBS_stats_magic	standard	727	9
fluxes_CBS_stats	minmax	876	27
fluxes_CBS_stats	standard	876	43
fluxes_CHRR_stats_magic	minmax	1181	4
fluxes_CHRR_stats_magic	standard	1181	7
fluxes_CHRR_stats	minmax	1181	4
fluxes_CHRR_stats	standard	1181	7
sensitivity_CHRR	minmax	238	48
sensitivity_CHRR	standard	238	51
sensitivity_CBS	minmax	248	24
sensitivity_CBS	standard	248	29
sensitivity_CHRR_magic	minmax	232	45
sensitivity_CHRR_magic	standard	232	48
sensitivity_CBS_magic	minmax	245	10
sensitivity_CBS_magic	standard	245	12
sensitivityKnockOut_magic	minmax	11	3
sensitivityKnockOut_magic	standard	11	3
sensitivityKnockOut	minmax	38	5
sensitivityKnockOut	standard	38	12

A.2 Metabolomics biomarkers and meta-data

Figure A.1: Scaled heatmap of metabolomics markers (clustering selected by Silhouette) where columns represent metabolites, rows are associated to cells and colors are proportional to metabolites concentrations.

Figure A.2: Histology distribution of metabolomics clustering.

Figure A.3: Pathology distribution of metabolomics clustering.

Figure A.4: Primary site distribution of metabolomics clustering.

A.3 Clustering hyperparameters

Table A.2: Clusterings selected by highest NMI with the metabolomics benchmark.

Omic	Algorithm	Clusters	Silhouette	NMI
RNA-seq metabolic	Leiden	2	0.08	0.42
RAS	Leiden	2	0.07	0.40
pFBA	HDBSCAN	2	0.17	0.05
Sensitivity analysis	K-means	10	0.24	0.09
CBS mean	Leiden	8	0.04	0.10
CBS mode	K-medoids	5	-0.02	0.08
CBS median	Leiden	32	-0.03	0.08
Correlation CBS	Leiden	25	0.11	0.07
CHRR mean	Leiden	7	0.05	0.09
CHRR mode	Leiden	29	0.03	0.08
CHRR median	Leiden	12	0.06	0.09
Correlation CHRR	K-means	2	0.07	0.08

Table A.3: Clusterings selected by highest NMI with the metabolomics benchmark. In this case, the RNA-seq matrix was processed by MAGIC.

Omic	Algorithm	Clusters	Silhouette	NMI
RNA-seq metabolic	kmedoids	2	0.38	0.41
RAS	kmedoids	2	0.36	0.42
pFBA	agglomerative	9	0.07	0.23
Sensitivity analysis	agglomerative	3	0.29	0.26
CBS mean	leiden	7	0.42	0.30
CBS mode	leiden	5	0.24	0.32
CBS median	agglomerative	2	0.34	0.39
Correlation CBS	agglomerative	2	0.28	0.39
CHRR mean	agglomerative	3	0.35	0.33
CHRR mode	leiden	7	0.38	0.29
CHRR median	leiden	6	0.38	0.32
Correlation CHRR	agglomerative	5	0.11	0.28

